

SATISFACTORY

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LIST OF DEFINITIONS & ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
CIDEM	Common Information Data Exchange Model
DBMS	Database Management System
DSS	Decision Support System
KB	Knowledge Base
OE	Ontology Engineering
OM	Ontology Manager
ORSD	Ontology Requirements Specification Document
OWL	Web Ontology Language
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RDFS	Resource Description Framework Schema
SF	SatisFactory
TPS	Training Platform Specification
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
XDM	XML Documentation Markup
XML	Extensible Markup Language
XSD	XML Schema Definition
XSL-FO	Extensible Stylesheet Language Formatting Objects
XSLT	Extensible Stylesheet Language Transformations

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable is the output of Task 2.2 and describes the second and final version of the SatisFactory knowledge model for Human Resource optimization.

The first part of this document is devoted to the Purpose, Context and Scope of this Deliverable. In the subsequent sections of the document, we provide:

- Information about the background and State of the Art in *ontology engineering and semantic modelling*;
- Objectives and benefits along with the definition and main components of *semantic modelling*;
- Methodologies for building ontologies and the major ontology languages as well as the leading ontology tools;
- W3C standards used for the Semantic Web in order to link data, create vocabularies, query and Inference;
- Ontology Manager Design through application of the NeOn methodology and a hybrid approach for the semantic lifting of XML Schemas.

Therefore, the creation of the SatisFactory Ontology Network, is presented according to three scenarios:

- Scenario 1: Ontologies built from scratch
This section includes domain-specific ontologies that are designed to support the specific shop floor knowledge for the Business Cases Scenarios that will be used in this project.
- Scenario 2: Ontologies built from non-ontological resources
This section includes ontology models' specifications for the semantic enrichment of the Common Information Data Exchange Model (CIDEM). The design of the so-called data oriented ontology models is driven by the XML Schemas developed to support the information flow through the SatisFactory Platform. Therefore, two relevant examples are introduced, which show the semantic lifting of multiple industry standards, such as the R3D and the B2MML.
- Scenario 3: Reusing Ontology resources
This section includes a thorough description of the ontology networks and resources that have been exploited in this framework.

Finally, the last part of this deliverable focuses on Ontology Exploitation through Knowledge Visualization, Data Integration, Rules inferences, aiming at supporting the Human Resources optimization.

1. INTRODUCTION

The shop-floor knowledge management represents one of the core processes in the framework of the SatisFactory project, where different data are exchanged from and to many diverse sources by outlining a complex net of information.

The background of the work described in this deliverable is mainly related to the activities and tasks depicted in Figure 1, and it is strictly related to T2.2 “Knowledge modelling to support the human resource optimization”.

Figure 1: Ontology Manager – Input Output Design diagram

The main goal of T2.2 is to capture implicit and explicit knowledge at the shop floor level. Thus, knowledge modelling methods, like ontology engineering (OE), are used in order to perform this task. All actors involved at this stage, as well as processes and assets, are defined. Concepts and relations between them are the basis of the knowledge modelling approach. Sets of rules coming from prior “hands-on” knowledge and previous experience enrich the knowledge model in order to achieve Human Resource optimization, through models that have to be both human and machine understandable. All of this is achieved with the use of semantic technologies that will characterize both designing (T2.2) and deployment (T3.1) of the Ontology Manager (OM).

Therefore, the OM component is being designed in order to process the information and data collected within the CIDEM and transform them into semantic enriched instances that could be stored in the RDF repository for future utilization. As mentioned earlier, the exploitation of semantic technologies (such as Ontologies will allow the enrichment of the acquired information with semantic attributes that will add to the SatisFactory platform the ability to manage the workers knowledge.

The design of the Ontology Manager (OM) can be, thus, split in three main facets:

- Definition of Ontology Requirements Specification Documents (ORSD)
- Development of the semantic structures (ontologies)
- Definition of semantic-based rules

Ontologies development and Semantic Rules definition can be accomplished by leveraging the results and taxonomies provided by:

- D1.2 Use Case analysis and application scenarios description
 - T1.2 Models for actors and procedures interconnection
 - T1.3 Use Cases and Scenarios
- D1.3 SatisFactory Common Information Data Exchange Model
 - T1.4 Common Information Data Exchange Model (CIDEM), and
- the requirements set by the industrial partners.

More details will be given in the next sections.

Moreover, the completion of Task 2.2 will support both:

- T2.3 Context-aware incident detection engine to increase worker's comfort
- T3.5 Shop floor feedback engine and integrated Decision Support System

The following deliverable will, therefore, present different designing and modelling aspects that have been analysed and used to develop the OM, for example:

- Modelling languages and standards,
- Ontology development methodologies and tools,
- OM design architecture, and
- Ontology exploitation examples.

2. STATE OF THE ART

2.1 *ONTOLOGY ENGINEERING*

In the past 20 years, ontologies and their development have been the centre of attention. Ontology development has indeed become an engineering discipline. Ontology Engineering, refers to “The set of activities that concern the ontology development process and the ontology lifecycle, the methods and methodologies for building ontologies, and the tool suites and languages that support them” [M. C. Suárez-Figueroa et al., 2011].

2.2 *SEMANTIC MODELLING*

2.2.1 *Objectives and benefits*

The logical data structure of a so-called database management system (DBMS), whether hierarchical, network, or relational, cannot totally satisfy the requirements for a conceptual definition of data, because it is limited in scope and biased toward the implementation strategy employed by the DBMS. Therefore, the need to define data from a conceptual view has led to the development of semantic data modeling techniques. That is, techniques to define the meaning of data within the context of its interrelationships with other data. The real world, in terms of resources, ideas, events, etc., is symbolically defined within physical data stores. A semantic data model is an abstraction, which defines how the stored symbols relate to the real world. Thus, the model must be a true representation of the real world. The overall goal of semantic data models is to capture more meaning of the data. Benefits of exploiting them for business applications are mainly:

- **Avoiding misunderstanding;** by providing a clear, accessible, agreed set of terms, relations as a trusted source and discussions, misunderstandings can easily be resolved.
- **Conduct reasoning;** by being machine understandable and through the usage of logic statements (rules), ontology enable automatic reasoning and inference which leads to automatic generation of new and implicit knowledge.
- **Leverage resources;** by extending and relating an application ontology to external ontological resources, via manual or automatic mapping and merging processes, the need for repetition of entire design process for every application domain is eliminated.
- **Improve interoperability;** semantic models can serve as a basis for schema matching to support systems’ interoperability in close environments where systems, tools and data sources have no common recognition of data type and relationships.

Ontologies play an important role for many knowledge-intensive applications, since they provide formal models of domain knowledge that can be exploited in different ways.

2.2.2 *Definition and main components*

The term “ontology” was taken from Philosophy, where it means a systematic explanation of being. There are many definitions about what an ontology is and such definitions have changed and evolved over the years. However, Studer and colleagues [Studer et al., 1998] provide one of the most well-

known definitions: “An ontology is a formal, explicit specification of a shared conceptualization”. *Conceptualization* refers to an abstract model of some phenomenon in the world by having identified the relevant concepts of that phenomenon. *Explicit* means that the type of concepts used, and the constraints on their use are explicitly defined. *Formal* refers to the fact that the ontology should be machine-readable. *Shared* reflects the notion that an ontology captures consensual knowledge, i.e. it is not private for some individual, but accepted by a group.

Ontologies can be modeled with different knowledge modeling techniques and they can be implemented in various kinds of languages based on different knowledge representation formalisms. It is important to mention here that there are connections and implications between the knowledge modeling components (concepts, roles, etc.) used to build an ontology, the knowledge representation paradigms (frames, description logics, logic) used to formally represent such components, and the languages used to implement the ontologies under a given knowledge representation paradigm. However, they share the following minimal set of components:

- **Classes** represent concepts, which are taken in a broad sense. For instance, in the domain of Energy Efficiency at Buildings, concepts are Building, Door, Window, Device, Sensor, etc. Classes in the ontology are usually organized in taxonomies through which inheritance mechanisms can be applied. We can represent a taxonomy of sensors (Scanning Sensor, Optical Sensor, Touch Trigger Sensor, etc.) or different types of doors in buildings (Inner Door, Outer Door, Sliding Door, Rotating Door, or Strong room Door).
- **Relations** represent a type of association between concepts of the domain. They are formally defined as any subset of a product of n sets, that is: $R \subset C_1 \times C_2 \times \dots \times C_n$. Ontologies usually contain binary relations. The first argument is known as the domain of the relation, and the second argument is the range. For instance, the binary relation *locatedIn* has the concept Building as its domain and the concept Location as its range; in addition, this relation can have the concept Device as domain. Binary relations are sometimes used to express concept attributes (aka slots). These attributes (*name*, *version*, *weight*, etc.) are usually distinguished from relations (*isComposeOf*, *hasConstraint*, *hasParameters*, etc.) because their range is a datatype, such as string, number, etc., while the range of relations is a concept.
- **Formal axioms**, according to [Gruber et al., 1993], serve to model sentences that are always true. They are normally used to represent knowledge that cannot be formally defined by the other components. In addition, formal axioms are used to verify the consistency of the ontology itself or the consistency of the knowledge stored in a knowledgebase. Formal axioms are very useful to infer new knowledge. An axiom in the Energy Efficiency at Buildings domain could be that it is not possible to build a public building without a fire door (based on legal issues).
- **Instances** are used to represent elements or individuals in an ontology.

2.2.3 Foremost methodologies for building ontologies

METHONTOLOGY², On-To-Knowledge³, and DILIGENT⁴ were up to 2009 the most referred methodologies for building ontologies. These methodologies mainly include guidelines for single ontology construction ranging from ontology specification to ontology implementation and they are mainly targeted to ontology researchers. In contrast to the aforementioned approaches, a new

² <http://semanticweb.org/wiki/METHONTOLOGY>

³ <http://www.ontotext.com/research/otk>

⁴ <http://semanticweb.org/wiki/DILIGENT>

methodology, called the NeOn⁵ Methodology, suggests pathways and activities for a variety of scenarios, instead of prescribing a rigid workflow.

METHONTOLOGY [A. Gomez-Perez, 2004] enables the construction of ontologies at the knowledge level. It includes (a) the identification of the Ontology Development Process – ODP – which tasks should be performed when building ontologies; (b) a life cycle based on evolving prototypes; and (c) some techniques to carry out management, development-oriented, and support activities. In addition, METHONTOLOGY includes a list of activities to be carried out during ontology reuse and re-engineering processes, but it does not provide detailed guidelines for such activities, nor does it consider different levels of granularity during the reuse of ontological resources (e.g., modules or statements). Moreover, METHONTOLOGY neither considers the reuse and re-engineering of non-ontological resources nor the reuse of ODP.

The **On-To-Knowledge** methodology [S. Staab et al., 2001] proposes to build ontologies taking into account how these are going to be used in knowledge management applications. The processes proposed by this methodology are the following: feasibility study, kickoff, where ontology requirements are identified, refinement, where a mature and application-oriented ontology is produced, evaluation, and maintenance. With respect to the reuse of knowledge resources, in the kickoff process it is mentioned that developers should look for potentially reusable ontologies. However, this methodology does not provide detailed guidelines for identifying such ontologies nor for reusing them. Besides, the methodology neither explicitly mentions guidelines for the reuse and re-engineering of non-ontological resources, nor for the reuse of ontology design patterns.

The **DILIGENT** methodology [H. S. Pinto et al., 2001] is intended to support domain experts in a distributed setting in order to engineer and evolve ontologies. This methodology is focused on collaborative and distributed ontology engineering. Its ontology development process includes the following five activities: building, local adaptation, analysis, revision, and local update. With regard to the reuse of knowledge resources, the methodology does not include guidelines for the reuse and re-engineering of existing knowledge resources.

Finally, the **NeOn Methodology** [M. C. Suárez-Figueroa, 2010] for building ontology networks is a scenario-based methodology that supports a knowledge reuse approach, as well as collaborative aspects of ontology development and dynamic evolution of ontology networks in distributed environments. A network of ontologies is a collection of ontologies related together via a variety of relationships such as alignment, modularization, version and dependency. The key assets of the NeOn Methodology are:

- A set of nine scenarios for building ontologies and ontology networks, emphasizing on the reuse of ontological and non-ontological resources, the reengineering and merging, and taking into account collaboration and dynamism.
- The NeOn Glossary of Processes and Activities, which identifies and defines the processes and activities carried out when ontology networks are collaboratively built by teams.
- Methodological guidelines for different processes and activities of the ontology network development process, such as the reuse and reengineering of ontological and non-ontological resources, the ontology requirements specification, the ontology localization, the scheduling, etc. All processes and activities are described with (a) a filling card, (b) a workflow, and (c) examples.

⁵ <http://www.neon-project.org/>

2.2.4 *Major ontology languages*

Different ontology languages have different expressiveness and inference mechanisms, since the knowledge representation paradigms underlying all these languages are diverse. Therefore, one of the key decisions to take in the ontology development process is to select the language (or set of languages) in which the ontology will be implemented.

An overview of the current specifications for ontology languages developed in the scope of the W3C Semantic Web Activity⁶ is presented.

- **RDF.**

RDF [G. Klyne et al, 2004] stands for **Resource Description Framework**. It was developed by the W3C to create metadata for describing web resources and its data model is equivalent to the semantic networks formalism, consisting of three object types: resources, properties and statements.

- **RDF Schema.**

The RDF data model does not have mechanisms for defining the relationships between properties and resources. This is the role of the **RDF Vocabulary Description language** [R. Guha, 2004] also known as RDF Schema. RDF(S) is the term commonly used to refer to the combination of RDF and RDFS. Thus, RDF(S) combines semantic networks with frames but it does not provide all the primitives that are usually found in frame-based knowledge representation systems.

- **OWL.**

OWL [M. Dean et al., 2004] is the result of the work of the W3C Web Ontology Working Group. This language derived from DAML+OIL [F. van Harmelen et al, 2001] and, as the previous languages, is intended for publishing and sharing ontologies in the Web. OWL is built upon RDF(S), has a layered structure and is divided into three sublanguages: OWL Lite, OWL DL and OWL Full. OWL is grounded on Description Logics [F. Baader, 2003] and its semantics are described in two different ways: as an extension of the RDF(S) model theory and as a direct model-theoretic semantics of OWL. Both of them have the same semantic consequences on OWL ontologies.

- **OWL 2.**

OWL 2 [B. Motik et al., 2009] is an extension and revision of OWL that adds new functionality with respect to OWL; some of the new features are syntactic sugar (e.g., disjoint union of classes) while others offer new expressivity. OWL 2 includes three different profiles (i.e., sublanguages) that offer important advantages in particular application scenarios, each trading off different aspects of OWL's expressive power in return for different computational and/or implementation benefits. These profiles are:

- **OWL 2 EL:** It is particularly suitable for applications where very large ontologies are needed, and where expressive power can be traded for performance guarantees.
- **OWL 2 QL:** It is particularly suitable for applications where relatively lightweight ontologies are used to organize large numbers of individuals and where it is useful or necessary to access the data directly via relational queries (e.g., SQL).
- **OWL 2 RL:** It is particularly suitable for applications where relatively lightweight ontologies are used to organize large numbers of individuals and where it is useful or necessary to operate directly on data in the form of RDF triples.

⁶ <http://www.w3.org/2001/sw/>

OWL 2 provides two alternative ways of assigning meaning to OWL 2 ontologies: the Direct Semantics that assigns meaning directly to ontology structures and the RDF-Based Semantics that assigns meaning directly to RDF graphs.

- **SPARQL.**

Even if it is not an ontology language, we mention SPARQL [E. Prud'hommeaux et al, 2008] here because it supports querying the previous languages. SPARQL allows performing queries over RDF data and, since both RDF-S and OWL are based in RDF, also over RDF-S and OWL ontologies. SPARQL can be used to express queries across diverse data sources and its syntax is similar to SQL to facilitate its adoption.

2.2.5 *Leading ontology tools*

Focus is given on the new generation of ontology engineering environments, particularly, on Protégé, described hereafter. They have extensible, component-based architectures, where new modules can easily be added to provide more functionality to the environment.

Protégé⁷ is an open platform for ontology modeling and knowledge acquisition. It is an open source, standalone application (also available on-line through Web Protégé), with an extensible architecture. The core of this environment is the ontology editor, and it holds a library of modules that can be plugged, called plug-ins, to add more functions to the environment.

The main Protégé functions are to:

- load and save OWL and RDF ontologies;
- edit and visualize classes, properties, and SWRL (Semantic Web Rule Language) rules;
- define logical class characteristics as OWL expressions;
- execute reasoners such as description logic classifiers; and edit OWL individuals for Semantic Web markup.

Protégé is available in different versions, each including different plug-ins and features. A quick overview of the stepwise enhancements introduced by the last two versions are presented below:

- Protégé version 4.3 supports for editing multiple OWL2 Ontologies and RDF. Moreover is allows in-memory connection to Pellet and FaCT++ reasoners⁸.
- Protégé version 5.0 offers enhancements and improvements in search, annotation viewing & editing, hierarchy viewing, ontology loading & saving, accessibility, logging and performance, as well as general user interface improvements. It also contains two new bundled plugins, "Cellfie" and the "SWRL Tab". Finally, Protégé 5.0 uses the OWL API version 4.2.5 and Java 8.

Open Semantic Framework (OSF)⁹ is an integrated software stack using semantic technologies for knowledge management, which includes an ontology editor. In particular, the OSF Ontology Tool is a user friendly environment provided by OSF through Drupal to create, modify, annotate or delete ontologies.

OSF for Drupal provides a set of already uploaded ontology sources that can be used towards the development of a custom semantic environment. The organization of the OSF Ontology application

⁷ <http://protege.stanford.edu>

⁸ Nowadays Protégé latest version is 5.0 Beta, which obviously still support OWL 2.0

⁹ <http://opensemanticframework.org/>

presents all the currently available and active ontologies listed in a specific panel. These are organized into three categories:

- Local Ontologies - these are the domain ontologies governing the use of the user's specific portal. They generally contain the "world view" and content organization specific to the user's problem or domain. Most of the editing and modifications will occur in this section. This is also the basis for the screen examples below;
- Reference Ontologies - these, too, are content ontologies, but generally represent external ontologies that can be re-used in the user's specific portal for interoperability or sharing purposes;
- Administrative Ontologies - these are internal ontologies that guide and govern the use of widgets, permissions, components and other administrative functions of the user's site. Most site administrators will have little or no reason to make any changes to ontologies in this category.

The **Anzo**¹⁰ software suite bundles a Semantic Web middleware platform and database with easy-to-use-tools that allow end users to convert existing data to Semantic Web data and to visualize, analyse, and act on the data. It includes the Anzo on the Web dashboard, reporting, and faceted browsing tool and the Anzo for Microsoft Excel component. It also includes such stables as an RDF database, a straightforward ontology editor, two rules engines, workflow capabilities, pub sub, and integration with XML data, relational databases, and Web services.

Anzo for Excel includes an (RDFS and OWL-based) ontology editor that can be used directly within Excel. In addition to that, Anzo for Excel includes the capability to automatically generate an ontology from existing spreadsheet data, which is very useful for quick bootstrapping of an ontology

Many other state-of-the-art tools can be exploited in order to develop the semantic structures that will be used to build the Ontology Manager. The most re-known are¹¹:

- Top Braid composer
- NeOn toolkit
- SWOOP
- Neologism
- Vitro
- Knoodl
- OWLGrEd
- Fluent Editor
- Semantic Turkey
- VocBench

More detailed information can be retrieved in literature.

Overall, this section sketched the essentials of foremost methodologies and technologies for building ontologies. Our main purpose is to select a relevant methodology to design the SatisFactory ontology models, as part of Task 2.2 activities, and a tool to implement the Ontology Manager, as part of Task

¹⁰ <http://www.cambridgesemantics.com/products/anzo-enterprise>

¹¹ <https://www.w3.org>

T3.1. Based on the conducted literature review, we have decided to partially apply the **NeOn** methodology, as it suggests straightforward pathways and activities for building ontology networks. Besides, this methodology supports a knowledge reuse approach, as well as collaborative aspects of ontology development and dynamic evolution of ontology networks in distributed environments. Whereas, the other methodologies (METHONTOLOGY, On-To-Knowledge and DILIGENT) do not provide guidelines for the reuse and reengineering of existing knowledge resources (ontological and non-ontological). This is a key driver in a context where several shop floor related resources exist, in terms of standards, ontologies, meta-data, glossaries, taxonomies, etc. Regarding the tools, we have selected **Protégé** (version 4), which support **OWL 2.0** and its profiles, as the main ontology editor, although ANZO Ontology Editor (ANZO for Excel) will be used in the framework of few application implemented with ANZO Enterprise.

2.3 W3C STANDARDS

W3C standards define an Open Web Platform for application development that has the potential to enable developers to build rich interactive experiences, powered by vast data stores, which are available on any device. Although the boundaries of the platform continue to evolve, industry leaders speak nearly in unison about how HTML5 will be the cornerstone for this platform. But the full strength of the platform relies on many more technologies that W3C and its partners are creating, including CSS, SVG, WOFF, the Semantic Web stack, XML, and a variety of APIs.

W3C develops these technical specifications and guidelines through a process designed to maximize consensus about the content of a technical report, to ensure high technical and editorial quality, and to earn endorsement by W3C and the broader community¹².

2.3.1 Semantic Web

In addition to the classic “Web of documents” W3C is helping to build a technology stack to support a “Web of data,” the sort of data you find in databases. The ultimate goal of the Web of data is to enable computers to do more useful work and to develop systems that can support trusted interactions over the network. The term “Semantic Web” refers to W3C’s vision of the Web of linked data. Semantic Web technologies enable people to create data stores on the Web, build vocabularies, and write rules for handling data. Linked Data¹³ are empowered by technologies such as RDF, SPARQL, OWL, and SKOS.

2.3.2 Linked Data

The Semantic Web is a Web of Data — of dates and titles and part numbers and chemical properties and any other data one might conceive of. The collection of Semantic Web technologies (RDF, OWL, SKOS, SPARQL, etc.) provides an environment where application can query that data, draw inferences using vocabularies, and the like.

However, to make the Web of Data a reality, it is important to have the huge amount of data on the Web available in a standard format, reachable and manageable by Semantic Web tools. Furthermore, not only does the Semantic Web need access to data, but *relationships among data*

¹² <http://www.w3.org/standards/>

¹³ <http://linkeddata.org/>

should be made available too, to create a *Web of Data* (as opposed to a sheer collection of datasets). This collection of interrelated datasets on the Web can also be referred to as Linked Data.

To achieve and create Linked Data, technologies should be available for a common format (RDF), to make either conversion or on-the-fly access to existing databases (relational, XML, HTML, etc.). It is also important to be able to setup query endpoints to access that data more conveniently. W3C provides a palette of technologies (RDF, GRDDL, POWDER, RDFa, the upcoming R2RML, RIF, and SPARQL) to get access to the data.

Linked Data lies at the heart of what Semantic Web is all about: large scale integration of, and reasoning on, data on the Web. Almost all applications listed in, say collection of Semantic Web Case Studies and Use Cases are essentially based on the accessibility of, and integration of Linked Data at various level of complexities.

2.3.3 *Vocabularies*

On the Semantic Web, vocabularies define the concepts and relationships (also referred to as “terms”) used to describe and represent an area of concern. Vocabularies are used to classify the terms that can be used in a particular application, characterize possible relationships, and define possible constraints on using those terms. In practice, vocabularies can be very complex (with several thousands of terms) or very simple (describing one or two concepts only).

There is no clear division between what is referred to as “vocabularies” and “ontologies”. The trend is to use the word “ontology” for more complex, and possibly quite formal collection of terms, whereas “vocabulary” is used when such strict formalism is not necessarily used or only in a very loose sense. Vocabularies are the basic building blocks for inference techniques on the Semantic Web.

The role of vocabularies on the Semantic Web are to help data integration when, for example, ambiguities may exist on the terms used in the different data sets, or when a bit of extra knowledge may lead to the discovery of new relationships. Consider, for example, the application of ontologies in the field of health care. Medical professionals use them to represent knowledge about symptoms, diseases, and treatments. Pharmaceutical companies use them to represent information about drugs, dosages, and allergies. Combining this knowledge from the medical and pharmaceutical communities with patient data enables a whole range of intelligent applications such as decision support tools that search for possible treatments; systems that monitor drug efficacy and possible side effects; and tools that support epidemiological research.

Another type of example is to use vocabularies to organize knowledge. Libraries, museums, newspapers, government portals, enterprises, social networking applications, and other communities that manage large collections of books, historical artefacts, news reports, business glossaries, blog entries, and other items can now use vocabularies, using standard formalisms, to leverage the power of linked data.

The complexity of the vocabulary that is used depends on the application. In some cases it might be decided not to use even small vocabularies, and rely on the logic of the application program. In other cases it might be chosen to use very simple vocabularies, and let a general Semantic Web environment use that extra information to make the identification of the terms. Finally, some applications may need more complex ontologies with complex reasoning procedures. It all depends on the requirements and the goals of the applications.

To satisfy these different needs, W3C offers a large palette of techniques to describe and define different forms of vocabularies in a standard format. These include RDF and RDF Schemas, Simple Knowledge Organization System (SKOS), Web Ontology Language (OWL), and the Rule Interchange Format (RIF). The choice among these different technologies depends on the complexity and rigor required by a specific application.

2.3.4 *Query*

In the framework of Semantic Web, the meaning of “query” is related to technologies and protocols that allows information retrieval.

The Resource Description Framework (RDF) provides the foundation for publishing and linking data, then, many technologies allow embedding data in documents, such as RDFa, GRDDL, or expose what is stored in databases, or make it available as RDF files.

The SPARQL has been designed to send queries and receive results, e.g. through HTTP or SOAP, within the Semantic Web, which is typically represented using RDF as a data format. This query language is based on (triples) patterns that are similar to RDF triples, and the results of a SPARQL query will be the resources for all triples that match those patterns. Thus, it provides a powerful tool that allows extracting complex information (i.e., existing resource references and their relationships) and present them in different friendly format (i.e. tables).

2.3.5 *XML Technology*

XML Technologies include XML, XML Namespaces, XML Schema, XSLT, Efficient XML Interchange (EXI), and other related standards.

2.3.5.1 *XML Essentials*

The Extensible Markup Language (XML) is a simple text-based format for representing structured information: documents, data, configuration, books, transactions, invoices, and much more. It was derived from an older standard format called SGML (ISO 8879), in order to be more suitable for Web use.

XML is one of the most widely-used formats for sharing structured information today: between programs, between people, between computers and people, both locally and across networks.

HTML and XML are very similar, however, the syntax rules of XML are strict: XML tools will not process files that contain errors, but instead will give you error messages so that you fix them. This means that almost all XML documents can be processed reliably by computer software.

The main differences from HTML are:

- All elements must be closed or marked as empty.
- Empty elements can be closed as normal, `<happiness></happiness>` or you can use a special short-form, `<happiness />` instead.
- In HTML, you only need to quote an attribute value under certain circumstances (it contains a space, or a character not allowed in a name), but the rules are hard to remember. In XML, attribute values must always be quoted: `<happiness type="joy" />`
- In HTML, there is a built-in set of element names (along with their attributes). In XML, there are no built-in names (although names starting with xml have special meanings).

- In HTML, there is a list of some built-in character names like *´*; for *é* but XML does not have this. In XML, there are only five built-in character entities: *<*, *>*, *&*, *"*; and *'*; for *<*, *>*, *&*, *"* and *'* respectively. You can define your own entities in a Document Type Definition, or you can use any Unicode character (see next item).
- In HTML, there are also numeric character references, such as *&*; for *&*. You can refer to any Unicode character, but the number is decimal, whereas in the Unicode tables the number is usually in hexadecimal. XML also allows hexadecimal references: *&*; for example.

XML has a number of advantages over many other formats. For any particular scenario, you might be able to come up with a better format, but then you would have to include costs of converting and processing your format, and of training, and of the XML-specific editing and searching tool that are now very widely available. Some of the advantages of XML include:

- Redundancy
 - XML markup is very verbose. For example, every end tag must be supplied, such as *</description>* in the example. This lets the computer catch common errors such as incorrect nesting.
- Self-describing
 - The readability of XML (it is a text-based format) and the presence of element and attribute names in XML means that people looking at an XML document can often get a head start on understanding the format (and it also helps people to find mistakes!)
- Network effect and the XML Promise
 - Any XML document can be read and processed by any XML tool whatsoever. Of course, some XML tools might want specific XML markup, but the XML format itself can be read by any XML parser: you can't say, this XML document is only to be processed by such-and-such tool
 - This means that every new XML document increases the value of every other XML document, and of every XML tool, and every new XML tool increases the value of every XML document and hence of every other tool. Today, XML is the most widely-used format of its kind, anywhere in the world.

2.3.5.2 *Efficient Interchange*

The EXI (Efficient XML Interchange) standard improves the performance, network efficiency, and power consumption of XML applications across the full range of use cases. Extensive testing shows that EXI performs consistently better than previous XML formats, data compression, and even packed binary data formats. As such, it brings the full range of XML benefits to even the most demanding applications.

EXI defines a compact encoding of an XML Info set for a wide range of usage scenarios, with a particular attention to keeping the necessary processing under control.

The EXI format uses a hybrid approach drawn from the information and formal language theories, plus practical techniques verified by measurements, for entropy encoding XML information. Using a relatively simple algorithm, which is amenable to fast and compact implementation, and a small set of data type representations, it reliably produces efficient encodings of XML event streams. The

grammar production system and format definition of EXI are specified in the EXI Format 1.0¹⁴ specification.

In addition to the EXI Format, the EXI Profile for limiting usage of dynamic memory is designed to accommodate very constrained devices (micro-controllers, sensors, etc.). In those environments, dynamic memory allocation is inexistent or very limited, therefore the EXI grammar learning mechanism needs to be controlled.

2.3.5.3 **Schema**

Schema languages and, in particular W3C XSD (XML Schema Definitions)¹⁵, are designed to express constraints about the structure of XML documents. In general, a Schema can be used

- to provide a list of elements and attributes in a vocabulary;
- to associate types, such as integer, string, etc., or more specifically such as hat size, sock color, etc., with values found in documents;
- to constrain where elements and attributes can appear, and what can appear inside those elements, such as saying that a chapter title occurs inside a chapter, and that a chapter must consist of a chapter title followed by one or more paragraphs of text;
- to provide documentation that is both human-readable and machine-processable;
- to give a formal description of one or more documents.

Information in schema documents is often used by XML-aware editing systems so that they can offer users the most likely elements to occur at any given location in a document. Checking a document against a Schema is known as *Validating* against that schema. Validating against a schema is an important component of quality assurance.

Since XSD supports associating data types with element and attribute content, it is also used for data binding, that is, for software components that read and write XML representations of computer programming-language objects.

2.3.5.4 **Transformation**

XSLT¹⁶ and XSL-FO are W3C Recommendations for defining XML document transformation and presentation. Use XSLT to transform documents into XSL-FO for printing or viewing; you can also use XSLT as a general XML-aware programming and transformation language, and you can use XSL-FO directly without XSLT.

A typical application might be taking groups of XML documents to PDF (see Figure 2)

¹⁴ <https://www.w3.org/TR/exi/>

¹⁵ <https://www.w3.org/TR/xmlschema11-1/>

¹⁶ <https://www.w3.org/TR/xslt>

Figure 2: From XSLT Transformation

XSL Transformations (XSLT 2.0) is a language for transforming XML documents into other XML documents, text documents, documents with RDF structure or HTML documents. You might want to format a chapter of a book using XSL-FO, or you might want to take a database query and format it as HTML.

With XSLT 2.0, processors can operate not only on XML but on anything that can be made to look like XML: relational database tables, geographical information systems, file systems, anything from which your XSLT processor can build an XDM instance. In some cases an XSLT 2.0 processor might also be able to work directly from a database of XDM instances. This ability to operate on multiple input files in multiple formats, and to treat them all as if they were XML files, is very powerful. It is shared with XQuery, and with anything else using XPath 2.0 (see Figure 3)

Figure 3: From XML documents merging

XSLT has become the language of choice for a very wide range of XML applications. It is of course still used to produce XSL-FO documents for printing, but it is also used to integrate back-end software for web sites. You will find XSLT inside most modern web browsers, so that XML can be transformed on the fly without the user even noticing. You will also find XSLT on the desktop, in servers, in network appliances, and forming a basic and dependable part of computer infrastructure almost everywhere you look.

3. ONTOLOGY DESIGN

3.1 OVERVIEW OF THE OM DESIGN

As mentioned in Section 2.2.3, METHONTOLOGY, On-To-Knowledge, and DILIGENT were till 2009 the most often mentioned methodologies serving to build ontologies. They mainly refer to guidelines for single ontology construction varying from ontology specification to ontology implementation; ontology researchers are usually targeting them. On the other hand, a quite new methodology (2010), the NeOn Methodology, suggests pathways and activities for different scenarios, instead of prescribing a rigid workflow.

Most of the methodologies described so far assume that ontologies have to be built first, then data schemas will be generated during the next designing phases according to the semantic structure. This is reasonable if we start from the assumption that **ontologies provide the vocabulary that will be used to classify and exchange information**. The designing approach of the Ontology Manager (OM), instead, will be different. This because, on the one hand the OM aims at semantic enrichment of CIDEM, while, on the other hand it aims at supporting specific Business Case Scenarios through the introduction of semantic structures that are suitable for the specific shop floor knowledge. The latter case doesn't introduce any new issue in terms of design, hence, it might be "canonically" tackled by leveraging the modelling techniques that are mentioned above. In this regards, from now on we will refer to this modelling approach as a top-down one. The first case, instead, introduces a non-trivial modelling facet. In fact, the semantic structures (ontologies) that are strictly built upon the shop floor data structure provided by the CIDEM documentation have to be modelled according to a so-called bottom-up approach, (see Figure 4) and thus, such ontologies have to be aligned to existing non-semantic sources, like the XSD schemas (gbXML, B2MML, R3D, MIMOSA, etc.) on which the CIDEM design is based on.

Figure 4: Semantic lifting of XML Schemas

Regarding the top-down modelling approach, the aforementioned NEON methodology has been adopted. For this reason, it will be further described in the following section. The bottom-up approach instead, have been tackled by customizing, and then, applying existing theories and methodologies in the field of XSD to OWL transformation [Yahia et al., 2012][Rodrigues et al., 2006].

Thus, the design and development of the entire Ontology Manager imply the hybrid adoption of both aforementioned approaches (top-down and bottom-up) and lead to a layered architecture that will be described in the next paragraphs. Therefore, the strength of the proposed design solution does rely on its networked architecture, which links together different nature ontologies and aims to provide a common vocabulary for the SatisFactory platform. In fact, on the one hand, such architecture provides a general vocabulary of classes and predicates for describing domain ontologies with the specific aim of promoting interoperability with external sources (such as datasets and domains). On the other hand, it aims at providing a coherent framework of broad subjects and topics, suitable as binding nodes for grounding relevant Web-accessible content, also with the specific aim of promoting interoperability and to reason over a coherent reference structure and its linked resources.

A relevant example of an ontologies network is given by the UMBEL Ontology (see Figure 5), which aims to provide a general vocabulary (the UMBEL Vocabulary) of classes and predicates for describing domain ontologies and presently counts of about 35000 concepts¹⁷.

¹⁷ <http://www.umbel.org/>

Figure 5: UMBEL Ontology

Thus, starting from the considerations presented above, the Ontology Manager has been imagined, and then designed, as a **Multi-Layered Ontology Network**. The **Top OM level** comprises the 3 shop floor Ontologies (COMAU, SUNLIGHT, CERTH) and aims at representing the knowledge that is related to each specific industrial partner and the related Business Scenarios (BSCs), and taking into consideration the HR optimization (see Figure 6). The **Middle Level** contains the SatisFactory Upper Ontology, which focuses on the three main shop floor concepts, such as *Assets*, *Procedures* and *Workers* and aims at providing a shared vocabulary by bridging the domain-specific ontologies at the top level with the so-called data-oriented ontologies at the lowest level. The **Low Level**, in fact, contains such data-oriented ontologies that have been derived from the CIDEM XML schemas, hence, strictly related to the information data structure, and then merged within the CIDEM Ontology (more details in Section 3.4).

Figure 6 provides an overview of the OM architecture by depicting the ontologies that span across the aforementioned 3 levels. These ontologies will be further described in terms of interoperability and practical implementation in the deliverable D3.1.

Figure 6: OM simplified architecture

3.2 *NEON METHODOLOGY*

As already mentioned in the previous section, the NeOn Methodology [M. C. Suárez-Figueroa, 2010] for the construction of ontology networks is “a scenario-based methodology that supports a knowledge reuse approach, as well as collaborative aspects of ontology development and dynamic evolution of ontology networks in distributed environments”. The key assets of the NeOn Methodology are:

- A set of nine scenarios for the construction of ontologies and ontology networks, focusing on the reuse of ontological and non-ontological resources, the reengineering and merging, and counting a lot on dynamism and collaboration.
- The NeOn Glossary of Processes and Activities defines the processes and activities carried out, when teams build jointly ontology networks.
- Methodological guidelines for a variety of processes and activities of the ontology network development process, such as the reuse and reengineering of ontological and non-ontological resources, the ontology requirements specification, the ontology localization, the scheduling, etc. All processes and activities are described with (a) a filling card, (b) a workflow, and (c) examples.

Following, the nine scenarios for ontologies and ontology networks building will be briefly presented:

Scenario 1: From specification to implementation. The ontology network is created from zero (without reusing existing resources). Ontology requirements are specified by developers [M. Suárez-Figueroa et al., 2009]. Later, it is suggested that a search for potential resources to be reused is conducted, in order to finally carry out the scheduling activity, so that developers are enabled to follow the plan for the development of the ontology network.

Scenario 2: Reusing and re-engineering non-ontological resources (NORs). Developers should carry out the NOR reuse process for deciding, according to the ontology requirements, which NORs can be reused to build the ontology network. Then, the selected NORs should be re-engineered into ontologies [B. Villazón-Terrazas et al., 2010].

Scenario 3: Reusing ontological resources. Developers use ontological resources (ontologies as a whole, ontology modules, and/or ontology statements) to build ontology networks.

Scenario 4: Reusing and re-engineering ontological resources. Ontology developers reuse and re-engineer ontological resources.

Scenario 5: Reusing and merging ontological resources. This scenario arises when several ontological re-sources in the same domain are selected for reuse and developers wish to create a new ontological resource with the selected resources.

Scenario 6: Reusing, merging and re-engineering ontological resources. Ontology developers reuse, merge, and re-engineer ontological resources. This scenario looks similar to Scenario 5, but here developers decide to re-engineer the set of merged resources.

Scenario 7: Reusing ontology design patterns (ODPs). Ontology developers access repositories (e.g., <http://ontologydesignpatterns.org/>) to reuse ODPs.

Scenario 8: Restructuring ontological resources. Ontology developers restructure (e.g., modularize, prune, extend, and/or specialize) ontological resources to be integrated in the ontology network.

Scenario 9: Localizing ontological resources. Ontology developers adapt an ontology to other languages and culture communities, thus obtaining a multilingual ontology [M. Espinoza et al., 2009].

According to the purpose and specifications of this work, we recognize the need for analysis and exploitation of the first three NeOn scenarios, as described above. Therefore, in the next sections we introduce a NeOn scenarios oriented description of the OM ontology models, which is more suitable from a designing perspective. In particular, we can distinguish the ontology development from scratch (Scenario 1), the transformation of non-ontological resources to OM ontologies (Scenario 2) and finally the reuse of already existing ontological resources (Scenario 3).

Ontology Requirements Specification, which is the activity of collecting the requirements that the ontology should fulfill, is presented. Such documents aims at defining the edges of the OM design, hence, it has been performed at the first stages of this task with all interested parties. The output of this important activity is the ontology requirements specification document (ORSD), which includes the purpose, the level of formality and scope of each ontology, the target group and the intended uses of the ontology, as well as a set of requirements, which are those needs that the ontology to be built should cover. The complete list of ORSDs can be retrieved within the ANNEX 1.1, 1.2, 1.3, 1.4, 1.5.

Figure 6 gives the big picture about the Ontology Manager (OM) ontologies network. Here we can distinguish the three aforementioned abstraction levels. In the next sections, instead, we aim to describe all the ontology models according with the NEON methodology. This further analysis plays an important role in defining the granularity and the required degree of detail of the SatisFactory Knowledge-Base (KB) at all levels.

3.3 SCENARIO 1 ONTOLOGIES

The so-called “Scenario 1 Ontologies” are all those semantic models that are built without reusing other ontological resources, and are developed from scratch. Within the SatisFactory framework such models are basically focused on specifying the shop floor context (COMAU, SUNLIGHT and CERTH), which have its own vocabulary and knowledge structure. Thus, in this section we give a brief description of the Shop Floor (domain-specific) Ontology models, whereas their potential exploitation in terms of HR optimization will be presented in Section 4. In the following paragraphs, we aim to describe what concepts are relevant in terms of piece of knowledge forming the whole Shop Floor Knowledge Base.

Hence, according with the ORSD template (see Table 1), the involved parties produced their Ontology Requirements Specification Documents in order to analyse the role of OM within their manufacturing context. Such documents can be seen in the ANNEX 1.1, 1.2, 1.3.

Table 1: ORSD template

ONTOLOGY REQUIREMENTS SPECIFICATION DOCUMENT	
1	Purpose (The general goal of the ontology. In other words, the main function or role that the ontology should have.)
2	Scope (The general coverage and the degree of detail that the ontology should have.)
3	Implementation Language (The formal language that the ontology should have.)
4	Intended End-Users (The intended end-users expected for the ontology.)
5	Intended Uses (The intended uses expected for the ontology.)
6	Ontology Requirements
	a. Non- Functional Requirements (General attributes and aspects, like terminology, qualities, and conventions, which are not related to the ontology’s principal content and the ontology should anyway try to respect. It may be written in natural language.)
	b. Functional Requirements (Must-have characteristics and specific functions which can manifest during the application. It may be useful to write it in the form of questions and associated answers.)

In the next sections, a description of the OM top level ontology models is provided. CERTH, SUNLIGHT and COMAU domains, indeed, are investigated in order to give a complete shop floor-oriented overview of the design aspects and issues that come up at this modelling stage. This can be further extended through the conjoint analysis of the Use Cases for the Ontology Manager in the framework of the BSCs (see Annex 2.1).

3.3.1 *CERTH/CPERI Ontology*

In this section, the CERTH/CPERI ontology is investigated as a whole, due to the fact that all application scenarios share most of the concepts and, obviously, the knowledge sources. Through the analysis of the BSCs description (see D1.2) and the ORSD, all the domain concepts and relations have been made explicit. These semantic elements will constitute the basis of the worker’s knowledge.

The BSC-5 “Online supervision of the operation and workforce resources of pilot plants for chemical processes” is taken from the daily needs of a semi industrial environment. This is the shop floor of CERTH/CPERI. There are several pilot plants with different procedures and functions within the shop floor. These pilot plants consist of many complicated components performing several procedures [D1.2]. BSC-5 can be furtherly discerned in three Application Scenarios that cover a set of activities, which are performed on daily basis at the shop floor of CERTH/CPERI:

- BSC-5.1 Repair or restore an electromechanical malfunction
- BSC-5.2 Start-up procedures of a Hydro cracking pilot plant
- BSC-5.3 Reconfiguration of process flow and actions for flexible redesign of production procedures

The BSC-6 “Recognition of accidents and path optimization for workers’ movement” is primarily focused on the safety of the workers. This is because the extent of CPERI’s pilot plants and the plethora of the necessary daily procedures impose numerous workers to spend most of their working time within high risk shop floor areas. In particular, the Application Scenario (BSC 6.1) refers to movement at the shop floor of CERTH/CPERI. The purpose of such case scenario is to analyse and reduce the number of accidents, while providing optimal paths to workers moving inside the shop floor.

Therefore, the main CERTH/CPERI Ontology concepts (classes) are listed down in Table 2, while Figure 7 gives an overview of their respective relations.

Table 2: CERTH/CPERI Ontology concepts

Concept	Description
<i>Workers</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Floor Manager • Maintenance Manager • Process Supervisor • Maintenance Supervisor • Process Operator • Process Technician • Automation Technician • IT Technician • Electrical Technician
<i>Working Areas</i>	Dedicated sections of the pilot plant
<i>BSCs</i>	Business Case Scenarios taxonomies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BSC-5.1 • BSC-5.2 • BSC-5.3 • BSC-6.1
<i>Physical Assets</i>	Equipment, inventory or machines
<i>Events</i>	Any event that takes place at the CERTH/CPERI shop floor, which can be classified (according to CIDEM) as follows: (i)Measurement, (ii)Alert, (iii)AR event, (iv)Maintenance, (v)ReAdaptation

- BSC-4.3 Training platform for production process motive power batteries assembly line

Therefore, the main SUNLIGHT Ontology concepts (classes) are listed down in Table 3 while Figure 8 gives an overview of their respective relations.

Table 3: SUNLIGHT Ontology concepts

Concept	Description
<i>Workers</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production Plant manager • Production planner • Maintenance manager • Production Supervisor • Production Line Workers • Foreman • Maintenance Technicians • Electrical Technicians • Process Technicians • Control Technicians
<i>Working Areas</i>	Sections of the pilot plant
<i>Business Case Scenarios Tasks and Procedures</i>	BSC task and procedures taxonomies, with focus on the specific Application Scenarios <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BSC-3.1 • BSC-4.1 • BSC-4.2 • BSC-4.3
<i>Physical Assets</i>	Equipment, inventory or machines
<i>Events</i>	Any event that takes place at the CERTH/CPERI shop floor, which can be classified (according to CIDEM) as follows: (i)Measurement, (ii)Alert, (iii)AR event, (iv)Maintenance, (v)ReAdaptation

Figure 8: SUNLIGHT Ontology

3.3.3 COMAU Ontology

BSC1 and BSC2 are the Business Cases Scenarios selected by COMAU for the implementation of the cutting-edge solutions presented by SatisFactory. In this framework, the exploitation of the OM aims at supporting the above-mentioned BSCs, yet in keeping with the ORSD defined by this industrial partner.

The BSC-1 “Operation activities of machine assembly at manufacturing procedures” focuses mainly on the production lines related to the operations that are necessary for the mechanical assembly and the manual assembly of components such as a robotized arm or a welding gun. There are two application scenarios involved that cover a subset of activities that are performed at daily basis at the shop floor of COMAU [D1.2]:

- BSC-1.1 Manual assembly operations with focus on Robot Wrist assembly
- BSC-1.2 Automated assembly operations with focus on Welding Gun assembly

The BSC-2 “Support of the components of production lines for intermittent operation” deals with activities that support the operations that take place at COMAU’S shop floor. In particular, the Application Scenario 2.1 aims at supporting the remote maintenance at manufacturing production lines.

Therefore, the main COMAU Ontology model elements, such as classes and sub classes (objects) are following described (see Table 4), while Figure 9 shows its structure by making explicit the main object properties.

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Table 4: COMAU Ontology concepts

Concept	Description
<i>Workers</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Process Operators• Maintenance Supervisors• Maintenance Technicians• Maintenance Managers• Design Engineers• Ergonomic Engineers
<i>Working Areas</i>	Dedicated sections of the pilot plant, such as production lines or assembly workstations.
<i>BSCs</i>	BSC task and procedures taxonomies, with focus on the specific Application Scenarios <ul style="list-style-type: none">• BSC-1.1• BSC-1.2• BSC-2.1
<i>Physical Assets</i>	Equipment, inventory or machines
<i>Events</i>	Any event that takes place at the CERTH/CPERI shop floor, which can be classified (according to CIDEM) as follows: (i)Measurement, (ii)Alert, (iii)AR event, (iv)Maintenance, (v)ReAdaptation

Figure 9: COMAU Ontology

3.4 SCENARIO 2 ONTOLOGIES

The Common Information Data Exchange Model (CIDEM) is defined according to the XML schemas, which have been designed for different domains within T1.4. According to these schemas, which basically define a list of elements and attributes in a domain-specific vocabulary, it is possible to apply the bottom-up approach introduced in Section 3.1 and build ontologies that provide a semantic representation (or semantic lifting) of the information data exchanged through the CIDEM, and then, bridging the lack of support for reasoning. Ontologies, in fact, can provide a semantic representation of domain knowledge which supports efficient reasoning and expressive power.

In this section, two XSD to OWL semantic lifting examples are introduced in order to give a preliminary description of how such transformation technique can be applied together with an overview of the main strength points and drawbacks of such modelling approach. The analysis of such data-oriented (“low level”) ontologies represents a relevant contribution toward the development of the so-called CIDEM Ontology (see Figure 10).

SATISFACTORY

Figure 10: CIDEM Ontology

As already introduced in D2.2.1, all the XML schemas have been translated through the application of a stepwise process described as follow (see Figure 11):

1. The XML Schema (XSD) given as input is analysed
2. We build an XML- Schema Graph (XSG) that describes the schema in the same way whatever its design style is. An XSG is basically composed of a vertex set, and an edge set. The vertex set contains all elements, attributes, non-primitive types, element groups and attribute groups. The edge set contains the edges established:
 - a. From each element to its type (if not primitive),
 - b. From each type, element group or attribute group to their contained elements and/or attributes. This phase is not visible; we focus on the final product, i.e. the ontology.
3. Given the XSG as input, we generate OWL entities. Basically, OWL Classes emerge from complex types, element group declarations, and attribute-group declarations according to sets of rules that will be further discussed in the next version.

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Figure 11: From XSD to OWL

Therefore, in the following section the R3D and B2MML XSD-OWL transformation examples are presented in order to provide an overview of the methodology described above applied to SF XSDs.

3.4.1 Low Level Ontology example - R3D

R3D is the Online Real-time Standard Operating Procedure Model. This model is serialized as an XML schema. It is important to point out that this model is deeply based on a “linked resources” approach. Thus lot information are maintained not directly into XML, but are represented by the linked data (e.g. 3D model, images, animation, etc.). It has been used as base SOP model to implement an AR-based system, to support assembly steps of critical components for plants. It represents a core component of the software architecture designed by Regola, on which a lot of software modules, provided for Satisfactory, will be based. It represents one of the most effective choices, in order to maximize the results of the software components that Regola will provide to Satisfactory.

Figure 12 shows an excerpt of the R3D ontology that has been designed to semantically lift the R3D XML-schema and support the on-job training and educational activities performed within the shop floor. Following Tables presented in Annex 2.2 show the *Classes* and *Relations* that represent the structure of this ontology. In particular, almost 60 Ontology elements (*Classes* and *Object* and *Data Properties*) are further described.

Figure 12: R3D Ontology

3.4.2 Low Level Ontology example - B2MML

B2MML is an XML implementation of the ANSI/ISA-95, Enterprise-Control System Integration, family of standards (ISA-95), known internationally as IEC/ISO 62264. B2MML consists of a set of XML schemas written using the World Wide Web Consortium's XML Schema language (XSD) that implement the data models in the ISA-95 standard.

This ontology is so far the biggest one and required a lot of effort to be modelled. At the end of its designing phase, we could define *96 concepts* and *189 relations*, which are presented in detail within the Annex 2.1. Therefore, it is taught to present an image that shows the whole B2MML ontology. Next two images (Figure 13 and Figure 14) show the so-called neighbourhood of two important concepts of the B2MML vocabulary, such as *Physical Asset, Equipment*.

development of the Ontology Manager. In particular, the shop floor data coming from the CIDEM and have been RDFized according to the vocabularies provided by the Ontology Manager will be further annotated with irON, SKOS and FOAF tags. A thorough description an analysis of their characteristics is, therefore, presented below.

3.5.1 *irON Ontology*

The irON Ontology¹⁸ (instance record and Object Notation) is an abstract notation and associated vocabulary for specifying RDF triples and schema in non-RDF forms. Its purpose is to allow users and tools in non-RDF formats to stage interoperable datasets using RDF. The notation supports writing RDF and schema in JSON (irJSON), XML (irXML) and comma-delimited (CSV) formats (commON). The notation specification includes guidance for creating instance records (including in bulk), linkages to existing ontologies and schema, and schema definitions. Profiles and examples are also provided for each of the irXML, irJSON and commON serializations.

The irON notation and vocabulary is designed to allow the conceptual structure ("schema") of datasets to be described, to facilitate easy description of the instance records that populate those datasets, and to link different structures for different schema to one another. In these manners, more-or-less complete RDF data structures and instances can be described in alternate formats and be made interoperable. irON provides a simple and naive information exchange notation expressive enough to describe any data entity.

The notation also provides a framework for extending existing schema. This means that irON and its various serializations can represent many existing, common data formats and standards, while also providing a vehicle for extending them.

3.5.2 *SKOS Ontology*

The Simple Knowledge Organization System is a common data model for knowledge organization systems such as thesauri, classification schemes, subject heading systems and taxonomies. Using SKOS¹⁹, a knowledge organization system can be expressed as machine-readable data. It can then be exchanged between computer applications and published in a machine-readable format in the Web.

The SKOS data model views a knowledge organization system as a concept scheme comprising a set of concepts. These SKOS concept schemes and SKOS concepts are identified by URIs, enabling anyone to refer to them unambiguously from any context, and making them a part of the World Wide Web.

The Simple Knowledge Organization System therefore aims to provide a bridge between different communities of practice within the library and information sciences involved in the design and application of knowledge organization systems. In addition, SKOS aims to provide a bridge between these communities and the Semantic Web, by transferring existing models of knowledge organization to the Semantic Web technology context, and by providing a low-cost migration path for porting existing knowledge organization systems to RDF.

¹⁸ <http://purl.org/ontology/iron#>

¹⁹ <http://purl.org/ontology/sco#>

3.5.3 *FOAF Ontology*

The FOAF²⁰ ("Friend of a Friend") project is a community driven effort to define an RDF vocabulary for expressing metadata about people, and their interests, relationships and activities. Regardless of whether information is in people's heads, in physical or digital documents, or in the form of factual data, it can be linked. FOAF integrates three kinds of network: social networks of human collaboration, friendship and association. FOAF does not compete with socially-oriented Web sites; rather it provides an approach in which different sites can tell different parts of the larger story, and by which users can retain some control over their information in a non-proprietary format.

Lastly, being an RDF application means that FOAF can claim the usual benefits of being easily harvested and aggregated. And like all RDF vocabularies, it can be easily combined with other vocabularies, allowing the capture of a very rich set of metadata.

3.5.4 *Context Management Ontology Network*

The aim of the ontology network mIO!²¹ is to represent knowledge related to the context of the user (see Figure 15). The context of the user must include the user's local information (position, date), information from the environment (temperature, luminosity), personal tastes of entertainment (theater, sport), and social information (buddy list, agenda). Furthermore, this context should include information about the services that a user can produce and/or consume (availability, price), as well as information on the devices that a user can use (battery, cover).

The ontology network mIO! consists of a central ontology (mIO.owl) that links together a set of ontologies that describe different sub domains required for modelling the context. These sub domains are: Device, Environment, Power, Interface, Location, Provider, Internet, Role, Service, Time and User. It is interesting to note that during the ontology development project of mIO! ontologies were reused from both existing ontologies as well as ontological design patterns and not ontological resources. The development of ontology network mIO! consists of three phases, two of which have been completed and it is working on the third and last. In the following link (<http://mayor2.dia.fi.upm.es/oeg-upm/files/mio/mIO!-Ontology-Network-v4.zip>) you can find the current version of the ontologies, which correspond to the third phase of development.

²⁰ <http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/>

²¹ <http://mayor2.dia.fi.upm.es/oeg-upm/index.php/en/ontologies/82-mio-ontologies>

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Figure 15: Context Management Ontology Network

4. ONTOLOGY EXPLOITATION

4.1 *KNOWLEDGE EXTRACTION AND VISUALIZATION*

The Ontology Manager aims to capture knowledge that exists in the domain. This implicit and explicit knowledge is of great value for people who are trying to understand such domain. Knowledge extraction refers to the creation of knowledge from either structured (xml, relational databases) or unstructured (text, documents, images) data sources. The resulting knowledge needs to be both machine-readable and machine-interpretable, hence, it must represent knowledge in a way that unambiguously defines its meaning and facilitates inferencing.

Therefore, knowledge can be represented and visualized as a graph. The nodes of this graph can show the different concepts in the domain of interest and edges can demonstrate the various relations between concepts. By visualizing the ontology model, the domain knowledge may become much easier to understand. In fact, the several interested parties can navigate through the domain concepts and relations and come into conclusion regarding the nature of their problem (or simple question) more easily.

4.2 *DATA INTEGRATION AND SEMANTIC INTEROPERABILITY*

The application of the Linked Data principles for data integration, created and maintained in order to explore the shop floor knowledge, appears to be one of the key benefits for SatisFactory. Such principles are outlined as follows:

1. All kinds of conceptual things have HTTP URIs.
2. If I look up one of these URI, I get back some data in a standard format.
3. When I get back that information, it is not just a mere data but its description and relationships.

Therefore, one of the key benefits of Semantic Web technologies, as key enablers of Linked Data, is the creation of data stores using URIs for identifying resources and their relations. When someone looks up a URI, provide useful information, using standards, such as RDF and SPARQL.

In this context, it is worth emphasizing another key concept, the semantic interoperability, that is, the ability of a system to exchange data and information with unambiguous, shared meaning. This is a requirement to enable machine computable logic, inferencing, knowledge discovery, and data federation between systems.

4.3 *RULES INFERENCE*

Ontology as a domain modelling technique assumes existence of rules that express logic in relation co-dependencies. To clarify this concept we will use a simple example. In a case of ontology modelling a domain of car-ownership might have simple rules such as "Tom owns X car" and "X is a

German factory". In that case, rule inference will provide us a new knowledge saying "Tom owns German car". Rule inference engines do this automatically and can chain more than two rules and thus, provide us with more complex conclusions, resulting in more detail and a clearer model of the domain.

It is important to highlight that rule inference is a self-initiated process. It is a background process on all levels for all the concepts, every time that the ontology is edited or the set of rules is extended. End-users do not even need to be familiar with these processes. Inference results are expressed through wider range of allowed queries for knowledge. Under certain constraints embedded in graphical interfaces, user can ask a direct questions and be presented with an answer as long as the answer is reachable using rule chaining.

In general, Knowledge Visualization, Data Integration and Rules Inference represent the three main exploitation features leveraged by any Semantic Technologies-based models. In the next section, the exploitation of the Ontology Manager toward the support of Human Resource Optimization is presented.

5. SUPPORT FOR HUMAN RESOURCE OPTIMIZATION

Section 3 introduces the conceptual architecture of the Ontology Manager together with the description of each single ontology model on which the OM is based. Moreover, these have been further classified according to their purpose and design nature. In particular, we introduced data-oriented ontology (Section 3.4) and domain-specific ontology (Section 3.3) models, which are bridged through the SatisFactory (Upper) Ontology model in order to create an environment that aims to introduce semantic enrichment features within the SF platform. A snippet of the full model can be retrieved in Annex 3.1. Section 4 presents an overview of the general exploitation aspects and features with regard to the use of semantic technologies (such as ontologies). Therefore, this section introduces one of the key exploitation aspects of the designed semantics-enriched framework, although, a thorough description of the semantic-enriched framework together with some detailed implementation and exploitation examples will be given in the deliverable D3.1.

In the framework of T2.2, different application (exploitation) scenarios have been investigated. The development of an on-job training environment, for instance, which might require the analysis of the workers suitability for specific tasks, or the pure analysis of their skills in order to obtain a skills-oriented overview of the shop floor workforce, may leverage the networked and semantics-enabled nature of the Ontology Manager together with the power of SPARQL language in order to browse through the domain concepts and support specific tasks. This approach can be, hence, extended toward the support and optimization of the Human Resource (HR) or the Training Activities analysis.

The design and development of the *Training and Educational Platform* is assigned to task T2.5, which is led by REGOLA. This will be developed on the basis of tasks T1.1 and T1.3 and can be further enriched through the exploitation of the Ontology Manager. It is worth noting that the training/education will be performed “on job”. This means that the worker will receive useful information while performing standard activities according to his profile characteristics, such as *experience*, *skills*, and the like. This information is collected from the CIDEM, and then, transformed and loaded on the Ontology Manager RDF triple store so that the semantic framework can manage and provide them to the end user as response, for instance, to an off-line information request and other queries.

Much the same applies to the *Re-adaptation of production facilities and HR workload balancing*, which instead is assigned to task T2.4 and led by ISMB. Regarding this task, the need of performing transversal information and data researches, can require the exploitation of the OM in order to obtain enriched information that span across heterogeneous CIDEM data sources.

The Human Resource optimization through the exploitation of Semantic Technologies and, in particular, of the Ontology Manager, starts from the assumption that worker background (Actor Role + Experience Level) and task requirements are the two main features that will be driving such HR management support for analysis, along with historical data provided through CIDEM.

The Ontology Manager aims to provide a common vocabulary at the shop floor level, as mentioned in the previous sections. An excerpt of the ontology concepts extracted from the 3-levels OM structure is shown on Figure 16.

Figure 16: HR optimization support - Ontology model excerpt

The so-called shop floor knowledge is, hence, modelled by making explicit the domain concepts and the relations among them. Therefore, according to the Ontology Requirements Specification Documents (ORSDs) produced by the above-mentioned partners (see Annex 1) the following concepts will be taken into consideration whereas HR resources in combination with tasks requirements have to be analysed (see Table 5).

Table 5: Training Platform concepts

Concept	Description
Shop Floor Worker	<i>Managers and Engineers, Supervisors, Operators and Technicians</i>
<i>Task/Procedure (Domain specific concept)</i>	Task performed by the worker, characterized by <i>Time duration, Required Role</i> and <i>Experience level</i> .
<i>Devices/Tool/Equipment (optional)</i>	Set of available shop floor assets such as machines, tools, instruments and the like.
<i>Factory Area (optional)</i>	Area of the shop floor where a specific action has to take place.
<i>Personnel Detail</i>	Worker details such as <i>ID, Actor Role, Experience</i>
<i>Shop Floor Events</i>	All the events that take place at the shop floor level

Then, starting from the highest (shop floor oriented) concepts, it is possible to track their links up to their lowest (data-oriented) semantic representation and create a knowledge map (see Figure 17). In this framework, it is worth pointing out that any concept (class) or relation is unambiguously identified by a Unique Resource Identifier (URI). This latter characteristic enables two relevant factors:

- It guides the semantic enrichment of the shop floor data
- It enables to perform specific analysis and queries on the system.

Figure 17: OM worker concepts tracing

With regard to HR optimization, the visualization of the ontology concepts and relations makes the understanding of worker profiles much clearer. However, so far the latter is described by a few available information (see Figure 18), which need to be enriched in order to perform meaningful and robust analysis.

Figure 18: OM Worker Profile

Figure 20 shows an enhanced version of the worker-like concepts “visual explosion”. In fact, here 12 new concepts are introduced in order to enrich the worker profile, which can be grouped as follows:

- MWG Index
- SRE Index

Where, MGW and SRE respectively indicate a “Matchability” Index for Worker Groups and a “Suitability” Index for Requested Experience. These concepts enrich the worker profile through quantitative information that enables as well the assessment of such profiles suitability for specific tasks through SPARQL based queries (see Figure 19).

Figure 19: OM and SPARQL Queries

Figure 20: OM Enriched Worker Profile

The ontology models, in fact, can be queried by using the SPARQL language. Figure 22 shows an excerpt of the Protégé SPARQL Query Tab where results are presented in a tabular form according to

the query structure. RDF data regarding Worker Profiles and Task Requirements can be, then, reasoned, combined and visualized according to the human-machine understandable structure showed above. The outcome of the operations mentioned earlier will be, therefore, used to support any task that requires a thorough profile-based (or skill based) analysis of the workers.

Figure 21: Suitability Analysis - Histogram

SPARQL query

```

PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
PREFIX sf: <http://ict4sm.epfl.ch/files/content/sites/ict4sm/files/ontologies/sf#>
SELECT
?Actor ?Group ?Experience ((?MWG_Index ?SRE_Index) AS ?Suitability)
?Task ?ReqAG ?ReqEL
WHERE {
?Actor a sf:CPERL_Worker . ?Actor sf:hasInitials ?ActorInitials . ?Actor sf:hasActorGroup ?Group . ?Group a sf:ActorGroup . ?Actor sf:hasExperienceLevel ?Experience . ?Experience a sf:ExperienceLevel . ?Actor sf:hasActorID ?ID .
?Task sf:hasRequiredActorGroup ?ReqAG . ?Task sf:hasRequiredExperienceLevel ?ReqEL .

?Group sf:hasMWGIndexWith_FloorManager ?MWG_FM . ?Group sf:hasMWGIndexWith_ProcessSupervisor ?MWG_PS . ?Group sf:hasMWGIndexWith_MaintenanceManager ?MWG_MM . ?Group
sf:hasMWGIndexWith_MaintenanceSupervisor ?MWG_MS . ?Group sf:hasMWGIndexWith_ProcessOperator ?MWG_PO . ?Group sf:hasMWGIndexWith_ProcessTechnician ?MWG_PT . ?Group sf:hasMWGIndexWith_ElectricalTechnician ?MWG_ET .
?Group sf:hasMWGIndexWith_AutomationTechnician ?MWG_AT . ?Group sf:hasMWGIndexWith_ITTechnician ?MWG_IT .
?Task sf:hasSREIndexWith_ Experienced ?SRE_E . ?Task sf:hasSREIndexWith_Novice ?SRE_N . ?Task sf:hasSREIndexWith_Trainee ?SRE_T .

BIND ( IF(?ReqAG= sf:FloorManager, ?MWG_FM, IF(?ReqAG= sf:ProcessSupervisor, ?MWG_PS, IF(?ReqAG= sf:MaintenanceManager, ?MWG_MM, IF(?ReqAG= sf:MaintenanceSupervisor, ?MWG_MS, IF(?ReqAG= sf:ProcessOperator,
?MWG_PO, IF(?ReqAG= sf:ProcessTechnician, ?MWG_PT, IF(?ReqAG= sf:ElectricalTechnician, ?MWG_ET, IF(?ReqAG= sf:AutomationTechnician, ?MWG_AT, IF(?ReqAG= sf:ITTechnician, ?MWG_IT, "")))))) AS ?MWG_Index) .

BIND ( IF(?Experience= sf:Experienced, ?SRE_E, IF(?Experience= sf:Novice, ?SRE_N, IF(?Experience= sf:Trainee, ?SRE_T, "")) AS ?SRE_Index) .

FILTER (?Task = sf:NS_Task1 || ?Task = sf:NS_Task2 || ?Task = sf:NS_Task3 || ?Task = sf:NS_Task4)
}
ORDER BY ?Task

```

Actor	Group	Experience	Suitability	Task
Worker14	AutomationTechnician	Experienced	"0.3"^^<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#double>	NS_Task1
Worker18	AutomationTechnician	Novice	"0.18"^^<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#double>	NS_Task1
Worker1	FloorManager	Experienced	"0.3"^^<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#double>	NS_Task1
Worker2	ProcessSupervisor	Experienced	"0.4"^^<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#double>	NS_Task1
Worker12	ProcessTechnician	Novice	"0.09"^^<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#double>	NS_Task1
Worker9	ProcessOperator	Trainee	"0.0"^^<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#double>	NS_Task1
Worker6	ProcessOperator	Experienced	"0.8"^^<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#double>	NS_Task1
Worker11	ProcessOperator	Experienced	"0.8"^^<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#double>	NS_Task1
Worker7	ProcessOperator	Experienced	"0.8"^^<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#double>	NS_Task1
Worker5	ProcessOperator	Novice	"0.48"^^<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#double>	NS_Task1
Worker8	ProcessOperator	Experienced	"0.8"^^<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#double>	NS_Task1
Worker4	MaintenanceSupervisor	Experienced	"0.0"^^<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#double>	NS_Task1
Worker13	ElectricalTechnician	Experienced	"1.0"^^<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#double>	NS_Task1
Worker10	ElectricalTechnician	Experienced	"1.0"^^<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#double>	NS_Task1
Worker19	ITTechnician	Trainee	"0.0"^^<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#double>	NS_Task1
Worker15	ITTechnician	Experienced	"0.6"^^<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#double>	NS_Task1
Worker16	ITTechnician	Experienced	"0.6"^^<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#double>	NS_Task1
Worker17	ITTechnician	Novice	"0.36"^^<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#double>	NS_Task1
Worker3	MaintenanceManager	Experienced	"0.15"^^<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#double>	NS_Task1
Worker14	AutomationTechnician	Experienced	"0.18"^^<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#double>	NS_Task2

Figure 22: SPARQL Query Example

In this way RDF data, which contains the information together with its meaning and relations with the other single elements of the shop floor knowledge, can be, on the one hand, leveraged to make

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visible the worker knowledge, while, on the other hand, it can be used to perform any kind of analysis that might be further enhanced through the graph representation of the results. With this regards Figure 21 shows a histogram of the data obtained from the query in Figure 22. This result may guide the analysis of the worker profile, the distributions of the worker skills together with an easy-to-use framework for the retrieval of the most suitable worker for a specific task. This example, can eventually be enriched in the next phases in order to meet further requirements of the industrial partners.

Finally, in this deliverable an overview of the Semantic Technologies exploitation, with focus on Shop floor knowledge modelling and support for Human Resources has been provided. The implementation of the ontology models described so far and the description of the software stack selected for the deployment of the OM will be provided in the Deliverable 3.1.

6. CONCLUSIONS

In this final version of the deliverable regarding Knowledge modelling for Human Resource Optimization, we presented the background Knowledge Management Engineering techniques, modelling methodologies and standards that will be leveraged by the Ontology Manager (OM) in order to support SatisFactory functionalities.

By focusing on NeOn methodology for Ontology engineering and in particular on the first three scenarios proposed by the latter, this document presented a hybrid approach that leads to the creation of the SatisFactory network of ontologies which captures the explicit and implicit shop floor knowledge.

As part of Scenario 1, the presented semantic models, which are built from scratch, aim to model the concepts and relations of two business scenarios proposed by the industrial partners (CERTEH, SUNLIGH and COMAU). Hence, in the subsequent section (i.e. Scenario 2 Ontologies), we (i) presented already existing non-ontological resources (XML Schemas); (ii) performed the necessary transformations (semantic lifting) in order to enrich those resources; and (iii) built the ontology models that support the SatisFactory Common Information Data Exchange Model (CIDEM).

Therefore, the use of the semantic models in SatisFactory is presented through a number of exploitation scenarios. These scenarios include knowledge visualization, data integration, and rule-based inference. In particular, a practical application regarding the support of the Human Resources optimization is analysed.

Through the use of those exploitation alternatives, we aim to assist the deployment phase, which will be the subject of the next deliverable D3.1, i.e. Semantically-enriched framework for analysis and design of dynamically evolving shop floor operations.

In conclusion, this deliverable documents the effort spent during the first 18 months of the project and represents the actual status of the activities in Task 2.2. The models presented in this document should be perceived as a living asset that will grow while SatisFactory project proceeds.

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ANNEX

A1.1 ORSD CERTH/CPERI

ONTOLOGY REQUIREMENTS SPECIFICATION DOCUMENT - CERTH/CPERI	
1	Purpose
	The purpose of creating an ontology within the shop floor is to increase the utilization and accuracy of the information derived by the processes and systems in order to improve collaboration and sharing of knowledge.
2	Scope
	The scope of the ontology is to use data and information from existing and new structures within the shop floor and increase safety, controllability and performance of scheduled or unplanned actions and procedures in an online or offline manner.
3	Implementation Language
	The ontology will be implemented using Protégé modeling tool.
4	Intended End-Users
	<p><u>User 1. Managers and Engineers</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Floor Manager • Maintenance Manager <p><u>User 2. Supervisors</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Process Supervisor • Maintenance Supervisor <p><u>User 3. Operators and Technicians</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Process Operator • Process Technician • Automation Technician • IT Technician • Electrical Technician
5	Intended Uses
	<p>Use 1. Enhance the decision support and prioritization of actions based on online operation status</p> <p>Use 2. Analyze historical data to derive patterns of behavior and correlations at the process units</p> <p>Use 3. Receive selected subset of online data from the automation systems (I/O field network) of the process units</p>

	<p>Use 4. Optimize the time to inform involved workers about a potential problem/status of the involved systems</p> <p>Use 5. Organize the operation and maintenance (corrective, preventive) procedures into a structured and uniform way</p>
6	Ontology Requirements
	a. Non-Functional Requirements
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Users misunderstanding shall be reduced. • The healthiness of work shall be increased. • The system should solve problems, not add them. Thus, it should be human and machine understandable, as well as user friendly. • Workers flexibility shall not be inferred. • The system shall integrate with existing collaboration platforms. • Standards procedures documentation shall be accessible and easily handled by non-experienced employees.
	b. Functional Requirements
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How does the ontology help the improvement of the procedures? The system shall allow the time validation of performed actions. This would help the improvement of the procedures and would eventually save a lot of working time. • What kind of information might be exchanged among the involved actors? The system shall enable information exchange and online status monitoring for each workers. • Should the ontology include different workday schedules? The system shall manage both ordinary and extraordinary workday schedules. • Does the ontology take the alarms into consideration? The number of false alarms shall be reduced. The latter does not directly apply to the ontology but those information can be consumed within the ontology in any case. • What kind of information concerning the process should be included within the ontology? The system shall visualize the mapping of the process that is implemented in the unit onto the unit's components, e.g. it shall augment what pipes are currently in use and what kind of gas flows in each of them. • Should the system support maintenance actions? Maintenance procedures will be recorded in order to be available to actors when necessary. They could be access via a tablet or a pc and actors will be guided how to perform the specific action. • Should the system include information concerning personal protection equipment? All actions within the shop floor must be performed with the necessary safety measures. Thus, the system will remind the actor which measures must be used according to the performed action. • Should the ontology include smart devices (e.g., computers, tablets, smart glasses, sensors)? The system architecture shall incorporate tablet PCs, several kinds of sensors. • Should the system record the generic situation information? Plenty of information regarding the worker activities which are performed at the shop floor and the respective time-schedule combined with prioritization and criticality information will be consumed by the ontology. • Should the system monitor the shop floor status? Information regarding the status monitoring will be consumed by the ontology. The status monitoring system will provide all necessary information about the status of the shop floor to all actors.

SATISFACTORY

- Should different kind of training procedures have to be provided? Video or audio recorded procedures could be available for new operators and technicians.

A1.2 ORSD SUNLIGHT

ONTOLOGY REQUIREMENTS SPECIFICATION DOCUMENT - SUNLIGHT	
1	Purpose
	The purpose of creating an ontology within the shop floor is to increase the utilization and accuracy of the information derived by the processes and systems in order to improve collaboration and sharing of knowledge.
2	Scope
	The scope of the ontology is to use data and information from existing and new structures within the shop floor and increase safety, controllability and performance of scheduled or unplanned actions and procedures in an online or offline manner.
3	Implementation Language
	The ontology will be implemented using Protégé modeling tool.
4	Intended End-Users
	<p><u>User 1. Managers and Engineers</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production Plant manager • Production planner • Maintenance manager <p><u>User 2. Supervisors</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production supervisor • Foreman <p><u>User 3. Operators and Technicians</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production Line Worker • Maintenance Technicians • Electrical Technicians • Process Technicians Control Technician
5	Intended Uses
	<p>Use 1. Enhance the decision support and prioritization of actions based on online operation status</p> <p>Use 2. Receive work schedules for production and derive suitable battery string configurations per assembly steps</p> <p>Use 3. Analyze cell temperature data to derive patterns of behavior and correlations at the jar formation</p> <p>Use 4. Organize the maintenance works effectively and increase the working satisfaction of the involved actors</p>

	Use 5. Provide to the trainees all the necessary training information on-job, in order to perform the job correct and safely.
6	Ontology Requirements
	a. Non-Functional Requirements
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Users misunderstanding shall be reduced. • The healthiness of work shall be increased. • The system should solve problems, not add them. Thus, it should be human and machine understandable, as well as user friendly. • Workers flexibility shall not be inferred. • The system shall integrate with existing collaboration platforms. • Standards procedures documentation shall be accessible and easily handled by non-experienced employees. • Workers job knowledge will increased. • Workers will feel more comfortable and safe by using the on job training tool.
	b. Functional Requirements
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How does the ontology help the improvement of the procedures? The system shall allow the time validation of performed actions. This would help the improvement of the procedures and would eventually save a lot of working time. • What kind of information might be exchanged among the involved actors? The system shall enable information exchange and online status monitoring for each workers. • Should the ontology include different workday schedules? The system shall manage both ordinary and extraordinary workday schedules. • Does the ontology take the alarms into consideration? The number of false alarms shall be reduced. The latter does not directly apply to the ontology but those information can be consumed within the ontology in any case. • What kind of information concerning the process should be included within the ontology? The system shall visualize the mapping of the process that is implemented in the unit onto the unit's components, e.g. it shall augment what type of battery is currently assembled and it will provide the necessary schematic or drawing. • Should the system support maintenance actions? Maintenance procedures will be recorded in order to be available to actors when necessary. They could be access via a tablet or a pc and actors will be guided how to perform the specific action. • Should the system include information concerning personal protection equipment? All actions within the shop floor must be performed with the necessary safety measures. Thus, the system will remind the actor which measures must be used according to the performed action. • Should the system record the generic situation information? Plenty of information regarding the worker activities which are performed at the shop floor and the respective time-schedule combined with prioritization and criticality information will be consumed by the ontology. • Should the system monitor the shop floor status? Information regarding the status monitoring will be consumed by the ontology. The status monitoring system will provide the ontology manager of all necessary information about the status of the shop floor to all actors.

A1.3 ORSD COMAU

ONTOLOGY REQUIREMENTS SPECIFICATION DOCUMENT - COMAU	
1	Purpose
	The purpose of implementing an ontology within the shop floor is to ease the information flow between humans and machines and the fruition of real-time big data.
2	Scope
	The scope of the ontology is to exploit ICT and real-time data coming from the field in order to speed up communications, support decisions, documents access and enhance working conditions.
3	Implementation Language
	The ontology will be implemented using Protégé modeling tool.
4	Intended End-Users
	<p><u>User 1. Managers and Engineers</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design Engineers • Ergonomic Engineers • Maintenance Managers <p><u>User 2. Supervisors</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintenance Supervisors <p><u>User 3. Operators and Technicians</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Process Operators • Maintenance Technicians
5	Intended Uses
	<p>Use 1. Provide a training platform</p> <p>Use 2. Provide a support for production</p> <p>Use 3. Provide a feedback to engineering</p> <p>Use 4. Collect real-time data within the shop floor</p> <p>Use 5. Provide a support for maintenance</p>
6	Ontology Requirements
	<p>a. Non-Functional Requirements</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The personal misunderstanding shall be reduced. • The healthiness of work shall be increased. • An innovative training environment that allows multimedia training procedures and sessions shall be provided.

- Worker performances and quality shall be increased.
- Potential mistakes shall be reduced.
- The system should allow both tracking and monitoring activities, which are performed within the shop floor.
- The implemented system should be user-friendly.
- The system should respect employee's privacy.
- The system requires a quite powerful central hub collecting and computing real-time data.
- New trainings for the actors and additional maintenance are taken into account.

b. Functional Requirements

- Should the ontology include data from smart devices (e.g., computers, tablets, smart glasses, sensors)? Smart Sensing Networks for ergonomics monitoring, safety verification, workload planning. Offline/online ergonomics data availability is important to improve the workplace characterization.
- Should the system record standard training procedures? Training procedures have to be stored into the system and performed through multimedia platform.
- Should the system monitor the sequence of operations? Real-time information regarding the sequence of operations shall be provided by the CIDEM to assess potential mistakes.
- Should the system provide any kind of report? The application of terminals that guide the operators during the production process could lead to assisted production processes that generate automatically reports and checklists according to the operations performed.

A1.4 ORSD TRAINING/EDUCATIONAL PLATFORM

ONTOLOGY REQUIREMENTS SPECIFICATION DOCUMENT Training Educational Platform	
1	Purpose (The general goal of the ontology. In other words, the main function or role that the ontology should have.)
	<p>The purpose of implementing an ontology to support the Training (On-Job) Educational Platform is to enrich the information concerning the training activities with context aware knowledge.</p>
2	Scope (The general coverage and the degree of detail that the ontology should have.)
	<p>The training and Education Platform has the responsibility to provide dedicated services to support the activities of training and education not only to workers and machinery operators but also to manufacturing process supervisor.</p> <p>The scope of the ontology is to allow an automatic system, to interpret and properly manage resources, such as information related to shop floor operations, in order to support the so called On-Job Training.</p>
3	Implementation Language (The formal language that the ontology should have.)
	<p>The ontology will be implemented using Protégé modeling tool by leveraging W3C standard languages such as OWL and RDF.</p>
4	Intended End-Users (The intended end-users expected for the ontology.)
	<p>User 1. Foremen and coordinators User 2. Process operators</p>
5	Intended Uses (The intended uses expected for the ontology.)
	<p>Use 1. Generate a structure of big data covering shop floor activities Use 2. Enhance the communication network between humans and machines Use 3. Collect knowledge within the shop floor Use 4. Support and facilitate training activities</p>
6	Ontology Requirements
	<p>a. Non-Functional Requirements (General attributes and aspects, like terminology, qualities, and conventions, which are not related to the ontology’s principal content and the ontology should anyway try to respect. It may be written in natural language.)</p>
	<p>The system should allow humans and machines performances assessment.</p> <p>The system should solve problems, not add them. Thus, it should be human and machine understandable, as well as user-friendly.</p>

SATISFACTORY

	The system requires a quite powerful central hub collecting and computing real-time data.
	The system should allow clarity and transparency of information and communication.
	b. Functional Requirements (Must-have characteristics and specific functions which can manifest during the application. It may be useful to write it in the form of questions and associated answers.)
	The ontology must include the following concepts: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Operator• Activity<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ Standard Operating Procedures (SOP)○ Emergency Operating Procedures (EOP)

A1.5 ORSD INTEGRATED DECISION SUPPORT SYSTEM

ONTOLOGY REQUIREMENTS SPECIFICATION DOCUMENT	
Integrated Decision Support System	
1	Purpose (The general goal of the ontology. In other words, the main function or role that the ontology should have.)
	The purpose of integrating the Ontology Manager with the iDSS within the SatisFactory framework is to ease the reasoning of structured and unstructured information data that flow through the SatisFactory platform.
2	Scope (The general coverage and the degree of detail that the ontology should have.)
	Integrated Decision Support System is responsible for providing feedback to the decision makers regarding immediate or with lower priority actions needed in response to shop floor incidents, together with changes to manufacturing operations and processes and also maintenance operations and schedules. The Ontology Manager aims to enrich the Integrated DSS information flow with the shop floor knowledge.
3	Implementation Language (The formal language that the ontology should have.)
	The ontology will be implemented using Protégé ontology editor according to W3C standards, such as OWL2 and RDF.
4	Intended End-Users (The intended end-users expected for the ontology.)
	User 1. Decision Support System User 2. Knowledge Engineer User 3. Maintenance Manager, who wants to get quick overview upon a KBE solution, or Reports User 4. Production Manager, who wants to get quick overview upon a solution, concerning production line procedures User 5. Operational Supervisor
5	Intended Uses (The intended uses expected for the ontology.)
	Use 1. Provide a common and well-defined vocabulary for the SatisFactory platform Use 2. Capture the implicit and explicit knowledge regarding manufacturing processes and operations, maintenance schedules and procedures, production plans and details, worker activities and availability. Use 3. Provide a set of rules for reasoning and inferencing information. Use 4. Set up SPARQL endpoint, which will return RDF triples of de-referenceable URI's, in order to support and facilitate decision making process. Use 5. Interlink with pre-existing vocabularies for maximizing interoperability and re-usability.
6	Ontology Requirements

	a. Non-Functional Requirements (General attributes and aspects, like terminology, qualities, and conventions, which are not related to the ontology's principal content and the ontology should anyway try to respect. It may be written in natural language.)
	The OM should ease the decision making processed
	The system should require a dedicated repository
	The system should provide semantically enriched information data
	>>The OM should allow ad-hoc queries to ontologies
	b. Functional Requirements (Must-have characteristics and specific functions which can manifest during the application. It may be useful to write it in the form of questions and associated answers.)
	Is a parameter/variable outside of the predefined normal operation boundaries? >>The indication comes from Sensors Network, that 'knows' the normal values
	Has the parameter/variable surpassed the upper or lower limit of the normal operation boundaries? >>Same as above
	Where does the parameter/variable surpassing the normal operation boundaries come from? >>CIDEM holds the limits for the upper and lower values Which part of the plant/procedure, from which sensor? >>CIDEM has the information about the plant layout and sensors
	In which shop floor area there is an alarm for a high possibility for an accident?
	Who has access to the shop floor area where an alarm for a high possibility for an accident has been signaled?
	What safety procedure is followed for the certain accident type at the certain shop floor area?
	There is a need to change the production procedures from which product A to which product B? >>This is not automated decision but rather user initiated
	What is the standard operating procedure for terminating the production of product A? >>It's user Initiated
	What is the standard operating procedure for initiating the production of product B? >>It's user initiated
	Is the Preventive Maintenance Schedule available? >> From CMMS via IDSS. Will be stored to CIDEM as well
	What resources and tools are needed to implement the Preventive Maintenance Schedule? >>From CMMS via IDSS. Will be stored to CIDEM as well
	What is the failure code/report/type? >>DSSEvent

	<p>Where is the failure reported? >>ISMB via linksmart</p>
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A2.1 B2MML ONTOLOGY – MODELLING DETAILS

Class	Class
Description	PersonnelInformationType
DescriptionType	PhysicalAsset
Equipment	PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecification
EquipmentAssetMapping	PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationID
EquipmentAssetMappingType	PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationIDType
EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecification	PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationType
EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationID	PhysicalAssetClass
EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationIDType	PhysicalAssetClassID
EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationType	PhysicalAssetClassIDType
EquipmentClass	PhysicalAssetClassProperty
EquipmentClassID	PhysicalAssetClassPropertyType
EquipmentClassIDType	PhysicalAssetClassType
EquipmentClassProperty	PhysicalAssetID
EquipmentClassPropertyType	PhysicalAssetIDType
EquipmentClassType	PhysicalAssetInformation
EquipmentID	PhysicalAssetInformationType
EquipmentIDType	PhysicalAssetProperty
EquipmentInformation	PhysicalAssetPropertyType
EquipmentInformationType	PhysicalAssetType
EquipmentLevel	PhysicalLocation
EquipmentProperty	ProcessSegmentInformation
EquipmentPropertyType	PropertyID
EquipmentType	PropertyIDType
FixedAssetID	PublishedDate
HierarchyScope	PublishedDateType
HierarchyScopeType	QualificationTestSpecification
ID	QualificationTestSpecificationID
IdentifierType	QualificationTestSpecificationIDType
Location	QualificationTestSpecificationType
LocationType	TestResult
Manufacturer	TestResultType
Name	TestedEquipmentClassProperty
NameType	TestedEquipmentClassPropertyType
Person	TestedEquipmentProperty
PersonID	TestedEquipmentPropertyType

SATISFACTORY

PersonIDType	TestedPersonProperty
PersonName	TestedPersonPropertyType
PersonNameType	TestedPersonnelClassProperty
PersonProperty	TestedPersonnelClassPropertyType
PersonPropertyType	TestedPhysicalAssetClassProperty
PersonType	TestedPhysicalAssetClassPropertyType
PersonnelClass	TestedPhysicalAssetProperty
PersonnelClassID	TestedPhysicalAssetPropertyType
PersonnelClassIDType	Value
PersonnelClassProperty	ValueType
PersonnelClassPropertyType	VendorID
PersonnelClassType	Version
PersonnelInformation	VersionType

Object Property	Domain	Range
hasDescription	EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationType	Description
hasDescription	EquipmentClassPropertyType	Description
hasDescription	EquipmentClassType	Description
hasDescription	EquipmentInformationType	Description
hasDescription	EquipmentPropertyType	Description
hasDescription	EquipmentType	Description
hasDescription	PersonPropertyType	Description
hasDescription	PersonType	Description
hasDescription	PersonnelClassPropertyType	Description
hasDescription	PersonnelClassType	Description
hasDescription	PersonnelInformationType	Description
hasDescription	PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationType	Description
hasDescription	PhysicalAssetClassPropertyType	Description
hasDescription	PhysicalAssetClassType	Description
hasDescription	PhysicalAssetInformationType	Description
hasDescription	PhysicalAssetPropertyType	Description
hasDescription	PhysicalAssetType	Description
hasDescription	QualificationTestSpecificationType	Description
hasEquipment	EquipmentInformationType	Equipment
hasEquipmentAssetMapping	EquipmentType	EquipmentAssetMapping
hasEquipmentAssetMapping	PhysicalAssetType	EquipmentAssetMapping

SATISFACTORY

hasEquipmentCapabilityTestSpecification	EquipmentInformationType	EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecification
hasEquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationID	EquipmentClassPropertyType	EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationID
hasEquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationID	EquipmentClassType	EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationID
hasEquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationID	EquipmentPropertyType	EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationID
hasEquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationID	EquipmentType	EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationID
hasEquipmentClass	EquipmentInformationType	EquipmentType
hasEquipmentClassID	EquipmentType	EquipmentClassID
hasEquipmentClassID	TestedEquipmentClassPropertyType	EquipmentClassID
hasEquipmentClassProperty	EquipmentClassPropertyType	EquipmentClassProperty
hasEquipmentClassProperty	EquipmentClassType	EquipmentClassProperty
hasEquipmentID	EquipmentClassType	EquipmentID
hasEquipmentID	PhysicalAssetPropertyType	EquipmentID
hasEquipmentID	TestedEquipmentPropertyType	EquipmentID
hasEquipmentLevel	EquipmentClassType	EquipmentLevel
hasEquipmentLevel	EquipmentType	EquipmentLevel
hasEquipmentLevel	PhysicalAssetType	EquipmentLevel
hasEquipmentProperty	EquipmentPropertyType	EquipmentProperty
hasEquipmentProperty	EquipmentType	EquipmentProperty
hasFixedAssetID	PhysicalAssetType	FixedAssetID
hasHierarchyScope	EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationType	HierarchyScope
hasHierarchyScope	EquipmentClassType	HierarchyScope
hasHierarchyScope	EquipmentInformationType	HierarchyScope
hasHierarchyScope	EquipmentType	HierarchyScope
hasHierarchyScope	PersonType	HierarchyScope
hasHierarchyScope	PersonnelClassType	HierarchyScope
hasHierarchyScope	PersonnelInformationType	HierarchyScope
hasHierarchyScope	PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationType	HierarchyScope
hasHierarchyScope	PhysicalAssetClassType	HierarchyScope
hasHierarchyScope	PhysicalAssetInformationType	HierarchyScope
hasHierarchyScope	PhysicalAssetType	HierarchyScope
hasHierarchyScope	QualificationTestSpecificationType	HierarchyScope

SATISFACTORY

hasID	EquipmentClassPropertyType	ID
hasID	EquipmentInformationType	ID
hasID	EquipmentPropertyType	ID
hasID	EquipmentType	ID
hasID	PersonPropertyType	ID
hasID	PersonType	ID
hasID	PersonnelClassPropertyType	ID
hasID	PersonnelClassType	ID
hasID	PersonnelInformationType	ID
hasID	PhysicalAssetClassPropertyType	ID
hasID	PhysicalAssetClassType	ID
hasID	PhysicalAssetInformationType	ID
hasID	PhysicalAssetType	ID
hasID	QualificationTestSpecificationType	ID
hasLocation	EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationType	Location
hasLocation	EquipmentClassType	Location
hasLocation	EquipmentInformationType	Location
hasLocation	EquipmentType	Location
hasLocation	PersonType	Location
hasLocation	PersonnelClassType	Location
hasLocation	PersonnelInformationType	Location
hasLocation	QualificationTestSpecificationType	Location
hasManufacturer	PhysicalAssetClassType	Manufacturer
hasName	EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationType	Name
hasName	PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationType	Name
hasPerson	PersonnelInformationType	Person
hasPersonID	PersonnelClassType	PersonID
hasPersonID	TestedPersonPropertyType	PersonID
hasPersonName	PersonType	PersonName
hasPersonProperty	PersonPropertyType	PersonProperty
hasPersonProperty	PersonType	PersonProperty
hasPersonnelClass	PersonnelInformationType	PersonnelClassType
hasPersonnelClassID	PersonType	PersonnelClassID
hasPersonnelClassID	TestedPersonnelClassPropertyType	PersonnelClassID

SATISFACTORY

hasPersonnelClassProperty	PersonnelClassPropertyType	PersonnelClassProperty
hasPersonnelClassProperty	PersonnelClassType	PersonnelClassProperty
hasPhysicalAsset	PhysicalAssetInformationType	PhysicalAsset
hasPhysicalAsset	PhysicalAssetType	PhysicalAsset
hasPhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecification	PhysicalAssetInformationType	PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecification
hasPhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationID	PhysicalAssetClassPropertyType	PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationID
hasPhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationID	PhysicalAssetClassType	PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationID
hasPhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationID	PhysicalAssetPropertyType	PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationID
hasPhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationID	PhysicalAssetType	PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationID
hasPhysicalAssetClass	PhysicalAssetInformationType	PhysicalAssetClass
hasPhysicalAssetClassID	PhysicalAssetType	PhysicalAssetClassID
hasPhysicalAssetClassID	TestedPhysicalAssetClassPropertyType	PhysicalAssetClassID
hasPhysicalAssetClassProperty	PhysicalAssetClassPropertyType	PhysicalAssetClassProperty
hasPhysicalAssetClassProperty	PhysicalAssetClassType	PhysicalAssetClassProperty
hasPhysicalAssetID	PhysicalAssetClassType	PhysicalAssetID
hasPhysicalAssetID	TestedPhysicalAssetPropertyType	PhysicalAssetID
hasPhysicalAssetProperty	PhysicalAssetPropertyType	PhysicalAssetProperty
hasPhysicalAssetProperty	PhysicalAssetType	PhysicalAssetProperty
hasPhysicalLocation	PhysicalAssetType	PhysicalLocation
hasPropertyID	TestedEquipmentClassPropertyType	PropertyID
hasPropertyID	TestedEquipmentPropertyType	PropertyID
hasPropertyID	TestedPersonPropertyType	PropertyID
hasPropertyID	TestedPersonnelClassPropertyType	PropertyID
hasPropertyID	TestedPhysicalAssetClassPropertyType	PropertyID
hasPropertyID	TestedPhysicalAssetPropertyType	PropertyID
hasPublishedDate	EquipmentInformationType	PublishedDate
hasPublishedDate	PersonnelInformationType	PublishedDate
hasPublishedDate	PhysicalAssetInformationType	PublishedDate

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hasQualificationTestSpecification	PersonnelInformationType	QualificationTestSpecificationType
hasQualificationTestSpecificationID	PersonPropertyType	QualificationTestSpecificationID
hasQualificationTestSpecificationID	PersonType	QualificationTestSpecificationID
hasQualificationTestSpecificationID	PersonnelClassPropertyType	QualificationTestSpecificationID
hasQualificationTestSpecificationID	PersonnelClassType	QualificationTestSpecificationID
hasTestResult	EquipmentClassType	TestResult
hasTestResult	EquipmentPropertyType	TestResult
hasTestResult	PersonPropertyType	TestResult
hasTestResult	PhysicalAssetPropertyType	TestResult
hasTestedEquipmentClassProperty	EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationType	TestedEquipmentClassProperty
hasTestedEquipmentProperty	EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationType	TestedEquipmentProperty
hasTestedPersonProperty	QualificationTestSpecificationType	TestedPersonProperty
hasTestedPersonnelClassProperty	QualificationTestSpecificationType	TestedPersonnelClassProperty
hasTestedPhysicalAssetClassProperty	PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationType	TestedPhysicalAssetClassProperty
hasTestedPhysicalAssetProperty	PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationType	TestedPhysicalAssetProperty
hasValue	EquipmentClassPropertyType	Value
hasValue	EquipmentPropertyType	Value
hasValue	PersonPropertyType	Value
hasValue	PersonnelClassPropertyType	Value
hasValue	PhysicalAssetClassPropertyType	Value
hasValue	PhysicalAssetPropertyType	Value
hasVendorID	PhysicalAssetType	VendorID
hasVersion	EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationType	Version
hasVersion	PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationType	Version
hasVersion	QualificationTestSpecificationType	Version
isDefineAsPersonnelClassPropertyType	PersonnelClassProperty	PersonnelClassPropertyType
isDefineAsTestedPersonPropertyType	TestedPersonProperty	TestedPersonPropertyType

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isDefineAsVersionType	Version	VersionType
isDefinedAsDescriptionType	Description	DescriptionType
isDefinedAsEquipmentAssetMappingType	EquipmentAssetMapping	EquipmentAssetMappingType
isDefinedAsEquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationIDType	EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationID	EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationIDType
isDefinedAsEquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationType	EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecification	EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationType
isDefinedAsEquipmentClassIDType	EquipmentClassID	EquipmentClassIDType
isDefinedAsEquipmentClassPropertyType	EquipmentClassProperty	EquipmentClassPropertyType
isDefinedAsEquipmentClassType	EquipmentClass	EquipmentClassType
isDefinedAsEquipmentIDType	EquipmentID	EquipmentIDType
isDefinedAsEquipmentInformationType	EquipmentInformation	EquipmentInformationType
isDefinedAsEquipmentPropertyType	EquipmentProperty	EquipmentPropertyType
isDefinedAsEquipmentType	Equipment	EquipmentType
isDefinedAsHierarchyScopeType	EquipmentLevel	HierarchyScopeType
isDefinedAsHierarchyScopeType	HierarchyScope	HierarchyScopeType
isDefinedAsIdentifierType	FixedAssetID	IdentifierType
isDefinedAsIdentifierType	ID	IdentifierType
isDefinedAsIdentifierType	PhysicalLocation	IdentifierType
isDefinedAsIdentifierType	VendorID	IdentifierType
isDefinedAsLocationType	Location	LocationType
isDefinedAsNameType	Manufacturer	NameType
isDefinedAsNameType	Name	NameType
isDefinedAsPersonIDType	PersonID	PersonIDType
isDefinedAsPersonNameType	PersonName	PersonNameType
isDefinedAsPersonPropertyType	PersonProperty	PersonPropertyType
isDefinedAsPersonType	Person	PersonType
isDefinedAsPersonnelClassIDType	PersonnelClassID	PersonnelClassIDType
isDefinedAsPersonnelClassType	PersonnelClass	PersonnelClassType
isDefinedAsPersonnelInformationType	PersonnelInformation	PersonnelInformationType
isDefinedAsPhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationIDType	PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationID	PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationIDType
isDefinedAsPhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationType	PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecification	PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationType
isDefinedAsPhysicalAssetClassIDType	PhysicalAssetClassID	PhysicalAssetClassIDType
isDefinedAsPhysicalAssetClassPropertyType	PhysicalAssetClassProperty	PhysicalAssetClassPropertyType
isDefinedAsPhysicalAssetClassType	PhysicalAssetClass	PhysicalAssetClassType
isDefinedAsPhysicalAssetIDType	PhysicalAssetID	PhysicalAssetIDType

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isDefinedAsPhysicalAssetInformationType	PhysicalAssetInformation	PhysicalAssetInformationType
isDefinedAsPhysicalAssetPropertyType	PhysicalAssetProperty	PhysicalAssetPropertyType
isDefinedAsPhysicalAssetType	PhysicalAsset	PhysicalAssetType
isDefinedAsPropertyIDType	PropertyID	PropertyIDType
isDefinedAsPublishedDateType	PublishedDate	PublishedDateType
isDefinedAsQualificationTestSpecificationIDType	QualificationTestSpecificationID	QualificationTestSpecificationIDType
isDefinedAsQualificationTestSpecificationType	QualificationTestSpecification	QualificationTestSpecificationType
isDefinedAsTestResultType	TestResult	TestResultType
isDefinedAsTestedEquipmentClassPropertyType	TestedEquipmentClassProperty	TestedEquipmentClassPropertyType
isDefinedAsTestedEquipmentPropertyType	TestedEquipmentProperty	TestedEquipmentPropertyType
isDefinedAsTestedPersonnelClassPropertyType	TestedPersonnelClassProperty	TestedPersonnelClassPropertyType
isDefinedAsTestedPhysicalAssetClassPropertyType	TestedPhysicalAssetClassProperty	TestedPhysicalAssetClassPropertyType
isDefinedAsTestedPhysicalAssetPropertyType	TestedPhysicalAssetProperty	TestedPhysicalAssetPropertyType
isDefinedAsValueType	Value	ValueType

A2.2 R3D ONTOLOGY – MODELLING DETAILS

Classes	Object Property	Domain	Range
action	hasAction	step	action
description_layer	hasDescriptionLayer	description_layers	description_layer
description_layers	hasObjectID	objects	objectid
inventory	hasObjectID	objects_to	objectid
nodes	hasObjectID	objects_with	objectid
objectid	hasOperation	nodes	operation
objects	hasRelation	relations	relation
objects_to	hasStep	operation	step
objects_with	hasWarehouseElement	inventory	warehouse_element
operation	involvesInventory	procedure	inventory
procedure	involvesNodes	procedure	nodes
relation	involvesRelations	procedure	relations
relations	isDescribedByDescriptionLayer	action	description_layers
step	isDescribedByObjects	action	objects
warehouse_element	isDescribedByObjectsTo	action	objects_to
	isDescribedByObjectsWith	action	objects_with

Data Property	Domain	Range
a_type	action	string
amount	objectid	unsignedByte
amount	warehouse_element	unsignedByte
authors	procedure	string
code	action	string
code	operation	string
code	procedure	string
code	relation	string
code	step	string
code	warehouse_element	string
confidentiality_level	procedure	ConfidentialityLevel
creation_date	procedure	dateTime
description	action	string
description	operation	string
description	procedure	string
description	relation	string
description	step	string
description	warehouse_element	string

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dl_type	description_layer	DescriptiveLayerType
dl_value	description_layer	string
el_type	warehouse_element	ElementType
element_id	warehouse_element	string
entry_id	objectid	string
goal	procedure	string
internal_id	action	unsignedByte
internal_id	operation	unsignedByte
internal_id	procedure	unsignedByte
internal_id	relation	unsignedByte
internal_id	step	unsignedByte
is_direct	relation	boolean
name	action	string
name	operation	string
name	procedure	string
name	relation	string
name	step	string
name	warehouse_element	string
order	action	unsignedByte
order	operation	unsignedByte
order	procedure	unsignedByte
order	relation	unsignedByte
order	step	unsignedByte
preconditions	action	string
preconditions	operation	string
preconditions	procedure	string
preconditions	step	string
rel_type	relation	GraphElementSpecification
resource_type	description_layer	ResourceType
result	objectid	string
short_description	action	string
short_description	operation	string
short_description	procedure	string
short_description	relation	string
short_description	step	string
short_description	warehouse_element	string
source_id	relation	unsignedByte
target_id	relation	unsignedByte
version	procedure	string
weight	relation	unsignedByte

